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FOR UNDERGROUND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

**Ground-Structure Interaction of Twin Board Tunnels and Cross-Passages in
Soft Ground Pressure Balance Tunneling**

FINAL PROJECT REPORT

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16. Abstract With the increasing demand for tunnels in sensitive urban environments, pressure balance mechanized tunneling is employed in most soft ground tunnel construction projects. Segmental tunnel lining is used in pressure balance mechanized tunneling as temporary and final support. With common service life requirements of 100 and even 150 years, efficient design of pre-cast concrete segments can have considerable serviceability and economic importance. The aim of this thesis is to improve the understanding of ground-structure interaction of segmental lining in soft ground mechanized tunneling both in the main running tunnels and at cross-passage openings. Incorporating rare field data collected from the Northgate Link project in Seattle together with advanced three-dimensional (3D) finite-difference modeling (FDM), this research seeks to provide insight into segmental lining ground-structure interaction. As part of the effort to reduce surface settlement, pressure outside the TBM shield plays an important role in pressure balance mechanized tunneling. An advanced 3D FDM model is presented for pressure balanced tunneling, where the annulus between the shield and ground is full of pressurized material, simplifying the modeling of the shield. The FDM results show that the final lining loads are controlled by the shield and chamber pressure, and the modeling of the TBM shield is not required, as the ground convergence is smaller than the annulus gap size. Extending the 3D FDM model for cross-passages, an advanced 3D ground-structure interaction model is proposed for cross-passages connecting segmentally lined tunnels. Validated using field data, the results show the difference between the loading processes of the break-in and break-out. At the break-out opening, the loading process is controlled by the cross-passage opening formation, while at the break-in opening, the loading is controlled by the advance of the cross-passage excavation, as the ground confining the break-in area is gradually removed. The most critical points with regards to the load capacity of the cross-passage opening support elements were found to be the segmental lining above and below the openings, and the bicone dowel shear capacity. In addition, this thesis investigates the ground response of a tunnel excavated by pressure balance mechanized TBMs in soft ground characterized by the hardening-soil small-strain (HSS) model. A comprehensive parametric analysis using a series of 3D and axisymmetric FDM modeling is employed. The results show that longitudinal displacement profiles (LDP) assuming linear-elastic or elastic perfectly plastic (EPP) soil behavior compared to		

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

With the increasing demand for tunnels in sensitive urban environments, pressure balance mechanized tunneling is employed in most soft ground tunnel construction projects. Segmental tunnel lining is used in pressure balance mechanized tunneling as temporary and final support. With common service life requirements of 100 and even 150 years, efficient design of pre-cast concrete segments can have considerable serviceability and economic importance. The aim of this thesis is to improve the understanding of ground-structure interaction of segmental lining in soft ground mechanized tunneling both in the main running tunnels and at cross-passage openings. Incorporating rare field data collected from the Northgate Link project in Seattle together with advanced three-dimensional (3D) finite-difference modeling (FDM), this research seeks to provide insight into segmental lining ground-structure interaction.

As part of the effort to reduce surface settlement, pressure outside the TBM shield plays an important role in pressure balance mechanized tunneling. An advanced 3D FDM model is presented for pressure balanced tunneling, where the annulus between the shield and ground is full of pressurized material, simplifying the modeling of the shield. The FDM results show that the final lining loads are controlled by the shield and chamber pressure, and the modeling of the TBM shield is not required, as the ground convergence is smaller than the annulus gap size. Extending the 3D FDM model for cross-passages, an advanced 3D ground-structure interaction model is proposed for cross-passages connecting segmentally lined tunnels. Validated using field data, the results show the difference between the loading processes of the break-in and break-out. At the break-out opening, the loading process is controlled by the cross-passage opening formation, while at the break-in opening, the loading is controlled by the advance of the cross-passage excavation, as the ground confining the break-in area is gradually removed. The most critical points in regard to the load capacity of the cross-passage opening support elements were found to be the segmental lining above and below the openings, and the bicone dowel shear capacity. In addition, this thesis investigates the ground response of a tunnel excavated by pressure balance mechanized TBMs in soft ground characterized by the hardening-soil small-strain (HSS) model. A comprehensive parametric analysis using a series of 3D and axisymmetric FDM modeling is employed. The results show that longitudinal displacement profiles (LDP) assuming linear-elastic or elastic perfectly plastic (EPP) soil behavior compared to the more realistic HSS model can result in overestimation of pre-convergence prior to liner installation. This over-estimation of the pre-convergence by EPP MC is shown to be as much as 20%. A new LDP solution for HSS is proposed for application in pressure balance TBM tunneling in soft ground, and the practical application of the new HSS LDP solution is described.

1.1.

BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter will present the background to this thesis in three parts: (1) an overview of ground-structure interaction of segmental lining; (2) an overview of cross-passage ground-structure interaction; (3) an overview of the Northgate Link project in Seattle, and the field data collected and used in this research.

The construction method used for tunnel excavation and excavation support has great importance for ground-structure interaction and must be considered when choosing a design method (Moeller 2006). The focus of this research is on soft ground pressure balance mechanized tunneling (also known as closed-face tunneling or shield tunneling), supported by pre-cast segmental lining for the main tunnels, and sequential excavation method for cross-passage construction connecting twin bored tunnels. In the first part of this chapter, the existing approaches for ground-structure interaction in the estimation of structural tunnel liner loads are presented. In the second part of this chapter, the available literature on cross-passage ground-structure interaction is presented. In the third part of this chapter, the Northgate Link project in Seattle is presented in detail with rare field data from strain gauges installed in segmental lining rings, and convergence monitoring collected during cross-passage excavation.

1.2 Ground-Structure Interaction and Tunnel Lining Load Prediction

Whether 2D or 3D numerical modeling is used (or analytical solutions) tunnel ground-structure interaction is controlled primarily by four factors: ground-liner stiffness ratio, ground pre-convergence, the interface between the lining and the ground, and coefficient of earth pressure at rest (Moorak and Cording 2006, Behnen et al. 2015). While the last factor is straight forward, capturing the first three requires an understanding of the tunnel components, tunneling construction process, and how the different modeling approaches control the ground-structure interaction and load development. This section will discuss the different modeling approaches with a focus on segmentally lined tunnels constructed by EPB TBMs.

1.2.1 Ground Pre-Convergence

Modeling the ground-structure interaction with 2D plane strain analysis (by either numerical modeling or analytical calculation) requires assumptions to simulate the effects of the 3D tunneling process. One approach to accomplish this is the well-known convergence confinement method (CCM). The CCM addresses the three-dimensional problem of tunnel excavation and support as a two-dimensional problem of ground-structure interaction (AFTES 2001). The method approaches the problem using three main components (Figure 1.1). First is the ground reaction curve (GRC), which relates the internal pressure P_i , to the tunnel radial displacement, (convergence). Second is the support reaction curve (SRC), which links the radial displacement of the tunnel to the support pressure. Third is the longitudinal displacement profile (LDP), which relates the tunnel boundary displacement u , to the position of the tunnel face X , and support installation. The key purpose of the LDP is to link the position at which the support is installed to the tunnel convergence (using the GRC) and in turn to the support pressure (using the SRC).

Typically a normalized displacement ($u^* = u/u_{max}$) is estimated as a function of the normalized distance ($X^* = X/R_0$), where u_{max} is the maximum tunnel radial displacement at $X^* \gg R_0$, and R_0 is the tunnel radius. Various LDP relations have been proposed by different researchers for deep, circular tunnels in a non-gravitational isotropic stress field and in isotropic homogeneous ground. Panet and Guenot (1982), and Panet (1993) developed the first LDP equations for the linear elastic case behind the tunnel face that was later revised by Panet (1995):

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = 0.25 + 0.75 \left(1 - \left(\frac{0.75}{0.75 + X^*} \right)^2 \right) \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (2.1)$$

This solution is independent of soil properties. The maximum radial displacement u_{max} can be determined by analytical solutions or 2D numerical calculations for the analyzed case. Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) proposed a complete LDP solution (Eq. 2.2) that covered both the region ahead and behind the face.

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = \left(1 + e^{\left(1 - \frac{2X/D}{1.1} \right)^{-1.7}} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 1.1. Schematic representation of the relation between LDP, GRC, and SCC for use in the Convergence Confinement Method (after Fairhurst and Carranza-Torres, 2002).

Unlu and Gercek (2003) suggested that the LDP does not follow one continuous function, but two functions, with one describing the LDP ahead of the face (Eq. 2.3) and one behind the face (Eq. 2.4).

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = U_0 + A_a \left(1 + e^{\left(-B_a \frac{2X}{D}\right)} \right) \quad \text{for } X < 0 \quad (2.3)$$

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = U_0 + A_b \left(1 + \left(\frac{B_b}{B_b + 2X/D} \right)^2 \right) \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (2.4)$$

where $U_0 = 0.22\nu + 0.19$, $A_a = -0.22\nu - 0.19$, $B_a = 0.73\nu + 0.81$, $A_b = -0.22\nu + 0.81$, and $B_b = 0.39\nu + 0.65$.

Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) advanced the LDP relation to account for the effects of large plastic zone development, assuming perfectly-plastic conditions with no dilation. This solution is valid from the elastic case to an extended plastic zone case. The Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) LDP solution also covered both the region ahead of the face and behind the face with two different equations:

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = u_0^* \cdot e^{(X^*)} \quad \text{for } X < 0 \quad (2.5)$$

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = 1 - (1 - u_0^*) e^{-\frac{3X^*}{2R_p^*}} \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (2.6)$$

Here, R_p^* is the normalized plastic radius $R_p^* = R_p/R_o$, R_p is the plastic radius, and u_0^* is the normalized radial displacement at the face:

$$u_0^* = \frac{u_o}{u_{max}} = \frac{1}{3} e^{-0.15 \left(\frac{R_p}{R_o} \right)} \quad \text{for } X = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

It should be noted that while this solution was developed for unsupported deep tunnels in hydrostatic stress conditions and elastic perfectly-plastic ground, many soft ground tunneling projects are excavated through soil with in-situ stress ratios other than unity, and non-linear soil stiffness. Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2014) examined the limitation of using Eq. 2.5 and 2.6 for anisotropic stress states and supported tunnels. They found that the anisotropic stress state limits the accuracy of the standard LDP approach (Eq. 2.5 and 2.6). However, for practical purposes, it can be used based on isotropic stress state. A revised LDP was suggested by Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2014) as a function of the distance from the face and the support installation position:

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{0.6 \left(1 - 0.1 \frac{S}{R_o} \right) \left(\frac{S}{R_o} - 5 \frac{S}{R_o} - 1 \right)}} \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (2.8)$$

where S is the distance between the face and the support installation position.

It is also important to note that no literature was found on the effect pressure balance TBM tunneling on LDPs, where prior to the installation of the lining, the face of the excavation is supported by muck or slurry pressure, and the shield annulus is assumed to be pressurized as well. However, in common engineering practice, one approach is that u_{max} should be taken as the final radial displacement with an internal pressure according to the machine pressure, while for conventionally excavated tunnels, the LDP is calculated for the unsupported u_{max} .

1.2.2 Joint Behavior

Tunnel support stiffness has a significant influence on ground-structure interaction, where on the one hand, a stiffer support system will limit ground deformation; on the other hand, it will develop higher lining loads. The stiffness of the lining ring, being the overall capacity to resist deformation, is straight forward in the case of a cast-in-place concrete ring. However, in tunnels supported by pre-cast concrete segmental lining, the effect of the joints, specifically the longitudinal joints, has been widely studied and was found to notably influence overall lining behavior (Blom 2003, Do et al. 2013a, b, Arnau and Molins 2011a, b, and more). These joints have a lower ability to resist deformation compared to an intact segment and may reduce the overall ring stiffness. As illustrated in Figure 1.2, there are two types of joints: circumferential (ring) joints between two successive rings and longitudinal joints between segments in a single ring.

Figure 1.2. Illustration of segmental tunnel lining and TBM shield. The figure shows the circumferential joints between rings and the longitudinal joints between segments in the same ring (Arnau and Molins, 2015).

The effects of the joints are commonly addressed in calculations by one of two methods, the direct method and the indirect method. The direct method entails the modeling of each segment individually with a connection between them according to a specific relation. The indirect method simplifies the problem by reducing the rigidity of a continuous tunnel liner model by a reduction factor.

The indirect method simplifies the problem by reducing the rigidity of the continuous tunnel liner. This is commonly done by applying a reduction factor η , to the bending stiffness (EI) of a continuous tunnel ring (Eq. 2-9).

$$\eta = \frac{EI_{eq}}{EI} \quad (2.9)$$

One of the first approaches that took the segmental joint influence into consideration and is still widely used today is Muir Wood (1975). In this method, the reduction of stiffness is controlled by the number of joints and joint geometry. This reduction is performed by calculating the equivalent moment of inertia as follows:

$$I_{eq} = I_j + I_g \left(\frac{4}{n}\right)^2 \quad (I_{eq} < I, n > 4) \quad (2.10)$$

where I_g and I_j are the full moment of inertia and the segmental joint moment of inertia respectfully. The segmental joint moment of inertia is a geometric property determined from the joint neck thickness as follows:

$$I_j = \frac{a^3}{12} \quad (I_j \ll I) \quad (2.11)$$

Various testing programs have been carried out to examine the behavior of full-scale segmental tunnel lining systems (e.g. Hordijk and Gijsbers, 1996; Schreyer and Winselmann, 2000; Blom, 2002; Lu et al., 2006, Li et al., 2015; Jin et al., 2017; Caratellia et al., 2017; Gong et al., 2017). Few publications on experimental testing for segmental lining addressed the indirect method to model segmental rings. Among the few who have, Liu et al. (2017) found that under service loading, segmental ring behavior is consistent with that of a continuous ring with a back-calculated stiffness reduction factor. However, the value of the stiffness reduction or methods to calculate it were not discussed.

The direct rotational stiffness of joints is commonly discussed in experimental testing publications as by Luttikholt (2007), who found the Janssen (1983) model to represent the moment-rotation behavior of the joint most accurately. As tensile forces cannot be transferred between segments, and the normal force at the joint (either longitudinal or circumferential) has significant influence on the joint behavior. With a high normal force (longitudinal force at the circumferential joint and hoop force at the longitudinal joints) and low moments at the joint, the joint remains closed with only compression pressure on the entire cross-section. However, with a high bending moment, a gap will form when the pressure at the extrados/intrados becomes zero, leading to significant additional joint rotation. The Janssen model, based on Leonhardt and Reimann (1966), describes the joint behavior in the form of a moment-rotation relationship. First, while the joint remains closed with only compression pressure on the entire cross-section, the joint rotation is linear-elastic, described by Eq. 2.12. As the moments increase and the joints start to open (Figure 1.2), the rotational stiffness becomes non-linear, described by Eq. 2.13.

$$\left\{ \phi = \frac{Mh}{EI} = 12 \frac{M}{Ea^2b} \right\} \text{ linear portion} \quad M < \frac{1}{6}Na \quad (2.12)$$

$$\left\{ \phi = \frac{8N}{9baE \left(1 - \left(\frac{2M}{Na}\right)^2\right)} \right\} \text{ non-linear portion} \quad M > \frac{1}{6}Na \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 1.2. Segmental lining concrete hinge, according to Leonhardt and Reimann (1966).

1.2.3 Ground/Grout Liner Interface

In any tunneling problem, a ground-liner interface must be established. In the case of shield tunnels with segmental lining, cement grout is injected behind the shield, between the lining and the ground, and the pre-cast concrete lining is in contact with the grout and not directly with the ground. It is important to note that the interface of the relatively smooth surface of the pre-cast concrete segment is different from the interface between sprayed concrete (shotcrete) and the excavation surface.

For the ground-liner interface, only two extreme interface conditions are usually assumed for analytical solutions (Rankin et al. 1978): full-slip with no transfer of tangential stress between the liner and the ground/grout, and no-slip conditions allowing the transfer of the shear tangential stress between the liner and the ground/grout. In numerical ground-structure interaction analysis, the interface can also be modeled with frictional contact. A zero coefficient of friction in which no tangential shear stress is transferred between the lining and the ground is analogous to the full slip condition (Sedarat et al. 2009). With the smooth finished surface of the pre-cast lining segments, the shear failure criterion between the lining and the annulus grout can be assumed closer to full-slip with low friction and zero cohesion. The interface model connects the ground/grout medium and the structural element by a deformable link, usually described by an elastic or elastic-perfectly plastic relation with a failure criterion (most commonly the Coulomb shear strength criterion). A common rule of thumb of both the normal stiffness and the tangential stiffness is one hundred times the equivalent stiffness of the neighboring soil element (Do et al. 2013).

The use of one method over the second will affect both the bending moment and the thrust force of the tunnel lining. The full-slip assumption results in higher magnitude moments compared to no-slip, and an approximately uniformly distributed thrust force diagram around the tunnel liner. For the no-slip assumption, the thrust force diagram is

not uniformly distributed, and its minimum and maximum thrust depend on the in-situ stress orientation and magnitude.

1.3 Cross-Passage Construction

Despite the complexity of cross-passage construction, and the complex 3D ground-structure interaction behavior, little research is available in the literature on cross-passage openings. The work available is divided herein according to two categories: openings in circular tunnels with monolithic lining (shotcrete or cast-in-place concrete) and openings in circular tunnels with segmental lining.

1.3.1 Openings in Circular Tunnels with Monolithic Lining

Much of the scarce research available on cross-passage construction, covers the stress concentration around openings in circular tunnels with monolithic lining (Jones, 2007; Spyridis and Bergmeister, 2015; Battista et al., 2015; Li et al. 2016). Elastic closed-form solutions such as Kirsch are discussed in some cases for the prediction of stress redistribution in openings in tunnel linings (Jones, 2007, and Spyridis and Bergmeister, 2015). However, the ground-structure interaction strongly influences the stress redistribution in openings, as does the ground-liner stiffness ratio (Spyridis and Bergmeister, 2015).

Jones (2007) studied stresses in sprayed concrete tunnel intersections by 3D computational modeling and pressure cell measurements from the Heathrow Terminal 5 tunnel. The 3D model included a monolithic shotcrete liner modeled by linear-elastic shell elements connected to the Mohr-Coulomb soil medium. At a distance of 1 m from the opening, Jones (2007) found that the maximum axial stress concentration factor was about two, and the maximum bending stress concentration factor was about 1.5 for the base case model. These results showed good agreement with the pressure cell data from the Heathrow Terminal 5 tunnel. Jones (2007) concluded that the construction sequence and the explicit modeling of the ground-structure interaction controlled the stress concentration at the tunnels junction.

Spyridis and Bergmeister (2015) investigated ground-structure interaction with a circular cross-section of both parent and child tunnels with elastic ground behavior. The study focused on the influence of geometry and elastic characteristics of the soil (mainly Young's modulus) primarily using 3D numerical modeling. The ratio of the child tunnel over the parent tunnel diameter was 0.6, 0.75, or 0.9, and the ground stiffness varied between 25 and 100 MPa. The 3D models were calculated in three steps: (1) geostatic conditions, (2) excavation of the parent tunnel and installation of lining (wished into place without pre-convergence), (3) removal of the breakout (without soil excavation). The results showed that the soil stiffness and the diameter ratio have a strong influence on the axial forces and bending moments, where the former is more significant. With a decrease of the soil stiffness, the axial force and bending moment increase, and with an increase of diameter ratio, the axial force and bending moment also increase.

1.3.2 Openings in Circular Tunnels with Segmental Lining

The ground-structure interaction of cross-passage openings in segmentally lined tunnels is significantly more complicated than the monolithic case. As one or more rings in the segmental lining are normally cut, the compression hoop force action is broken

(Figure 1.3), and the stability of the ring is compromised (Lee and Choi, 2017). To address this, a number of temporary support elements are typically used. Most common are the full ring beam ('hamster cage'), vertical steel propping with or without a header beam, and steel segments. With little research available in the literature on cross-passage openings in segmentally lined tunnels, designers approach cross-passages with a high degree of conservatism, resulting in robust and costly temporary support elements. In recent years, coupling elements such as steel dowels and shear bicone dowels have been increasingly utilized (Lee and Choi, 2017, Walter et al. 2019, Ring 2019) and allow for reductions in construction costs and complexities. However, the use of these coupling elements represents a less conservative design approach, and the lack of literature and understanding of cross-passage construction and ground-structure interaction may increase the risk of failure in case of unexpectedly high loads.

Figure 1.3. Stress distribution around opening in segmental tunnel lining (Lee and Choi, 2017).^a

Kuyt et al. (2016) studied field data collected from cross-passage construction between twin segmentally lined tunnels in mixed ground conditions using data collected from the Brisbane Airport Link project. In this case, the cross-passage openings were supported by steel segments and hydraulic steel props (Figure 1.4). Vibrating wire strain gauges were installed on the opening steel segments, the steel props, and embedded within select reinforced concrete segments around the opening area. The first important ground-structure interaction process observed was the horizontal unloading effect on the running tunnel lining as the excavation advanced towards the breakout. As the excavation of the cross-passage advanced towards the break-in, redistribution of stresses ahead of the cross-passage face resulted in load redistribution in the tunnel lining at and around the break-in. However, Kuyt et al. (2016) found a relatively minor (10%) transfer of loads onto the segments surrounding the opening, as the ground and the installed steel jacking props took most of the hoop forces from the opening ring.

^a Figure 2.3 is also used in chapter 5.

Figure 1.4. Brisbane Airport Link project cross-passage monitoring components, including strain gauges in the concrete segments, hydraulic props, and steel segments. (Kuyt et al. 2016)

In recent years, the use of shear bicone dowels has been adopted in many cases to transfer the hoop forces from the opened to the adjacent fully enclosed rings (Figure 1.5). Depending on the inherent strength of the pre-cast concrete segment, the bicone may provide an allowable shear resistance on the order of 150-375kN per unit run of the ring (Lee and Choi, 2017). The capacity of the shear dowels themselves is sufficient in most cases; however, in combination with thin pre-cast segments (commonly 20-40 cm in thickness), the ultimate load capacity of the overall system (segment-shear dowel) poses a challenge due to failure of the concrete in shear. Gehwolf et al. (2016) conducted experimental tests on four different reinforcement layouts and found that the ultimate load capacity of the shear bicone system can change by as much as 85% between different reinforcement detailing. The coupling effect of the opening temporary support element has a significant influence on the structure stiffness affecting the soil-structure stiffness ratio, and in turn controls the load development. This has to be assessed by 3D ground-structure interaction analysis, which is commonly performed in design practice, but rarely documented in the literature.

Figure 1.5. Illustration of shear bicones in circumferential joint (Lee and Choi, 2017).

1.4 Segmental Lining Strain Gauge Field Instrumentation and Monitoring

1.4.1 Northgate Link Project Background

The Northgate Link Extension project includes 5.6 km of twin bored tunnels and 23 cross-passages. The tunnels run north from the University of Washington to Maple Leaf Portal in north Seattle. The twin bored tunnels were constructed using two earth pressure balance TBMs (EPBM) with excavation diameters of 6.64 m and a shield diameters of 6.44 m. The resulting 100 mm annular shield gap is larger than the vast majority of shield gaps that are typically on the order of 15-30 mm. The two tunnels were constructed with a center to center distance of about two diameters. The tunnels were supported with a single pass, gasketed segmental lining, 25 cm thick, and an extrados diameter of 6.25 m. Each ring is comprised of four full-size segments and key and counter key segments with a nominal width of 1.5 m, and a universal ring concept having an overall ring taper of 69.9 mm. The segment design concrete strength was 55 MPa; the segments were reinforced with wire mesh with primary D14 reinforcement bars.

The geology of the area through which the tunnels were constructed consists of complex and highly variable interlayered glacial and non-glacial soil deposits. As part of the geotechnical baseline report, the geological units were grouped into engineering soil units (ESU) based on their behavioral characteristics. All tunnel excavation was completed in the following glacially overridden ESUs: till and till-like deposits (TLD), cohesionless sand and gravel (CSG), cohesionless silt and fine sand (CSF) and cohesive clays and silts (CCS).

1.4.2 Instrumentation and Monitoring

As part of the design of the cross-passage openings in the segmental lining of the main tunnels, three circumferential joints at each cross-passage opening were supported with shear bicone dowel connectors. The shear bicone dowels were used to transfer the load from the two segmental rings that were saw cut to form the cross-passage opening, to the adjacent rings. To confirm the ring thrust forces in the segmental lining, 17 out of 23 cross-passage locations were instrumented with full Wheatstone bridge foil strain gauges connected by wireless RFID transmission. As

detailed in Table 1.1, a total of 34 rings were instrumented. Typically, two rings were instrumented at each of these cross-passages, excluding cross-passage-34 where three rings were instrumented and cross-passage-43 where one ring was instrumented. At 8 cross-passage locations, the instrumented rings were installed in the NB tunnel that was excavated first, and at 8 cross-passage locations, the instrumented rings were installed in the SB tunnel excavated second. At one cross passage (cross-passage-34), two rings were instrumented in the NB tunnel, and one ring was instrumented at the SB tunnel (Table 1.1).

Within each selected ring, three segments were instrumented – two full-size segments plus a key or counter key (Figure 1.6a). Each instrumented segment was outfitted with a set of two foil strain gauges welded to the reinforcement cage: one at the intrados, and one at the extrados, as shown in Figure 1.6b. The intrados strain gauge center axis depth from the segment extrados was 58 mm as the strain gauge is installed on #3 rebar (9.5 mm) welded to the underside of the longitudinal 14 mm diameter (i.e., away from the intrados concrete face) rebar welded to the primary reinforcement (14 mm diameter), and minimum clearance is 25 mm. The extrados sister bar was installed on the exterior of the longitudinal reinforcement resulting in a depth of approximately 37 mm for the extrados stain gauge center axis. Collection of the strain gauges readings required passing a flat panel RFID reading unit within 30 cm of the concrete surface in the vicinity of the embedded sensor. The monitoring schedule included an initial zero strain reading after the welding of the sister bars prior to casting, followed by readings every two weeks after segment installation.

Table 1.1. Instrumented ring number at each cross-passage.

Cross passage #	Instrumented ring # at NB tunnel		Instrumented ring # at SB tunnel	
CP-43	-	-	159	-
CP-41	-	-	464	462
CP-40	-	-	613	615
CP-39	-	-	745	747
CP-38	-	-	906	908
CP-37	-	-	1045	1047
CP-36	-	-	1205	1207
CP-35	-	-	1364	1366
CP-34	1506	1508	1507	-
CP-31	2028	2030	-	-
CP-30	2160	2162	-	-
CP-29	2313	2315	-	-
CP-28	2472	2474	-	-
CP-27	2571	2573	-	-
CP-24	3098	3100	-	-
CP-23	3242	3244	-	-
CP-22	3388	3390	-	-

Figure 1.6. (a) Cross-section of a typical instrumented ring, with the instrumented segments marked A, B & C. (b) Segment cross-section at strain gauge location (dimensions in mm). (c) Strain gauge location on a typical segment plan view d) Sign convention for bending moments and thrust force.^b

The orientations of the strain gauges allowed measurement of the circumferential strain and interpretation of the stresses developed in the pre-cast segments. With known geometry and strain gauge depth, the measurements collected from a set of two strain gauges allowed for the estimation of both thrust force (hoop force) and bending moment. The sign conventions used convey positive values for compressive thrust force and positive for bending moment when the segment intrados is in tension (Figure 1.6).

With practically no tensile strains in the reliable strain gauge field data, the concrete strain distribution between the strain gauge positions and along the entire cross-section height is assumed to be linear (Figure 1.7). With known cross-section geometry and strain gauge depth, the measurements collected from a set of two strain gauges allowed for the estimation of the strains at both the extrados and the intrados by the following relationship:

$$\kappa = \frac{\varepsilon_{s,int} - \varepsilon_{s,ext}}{z} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\varepsilon_{int} = \varepsilon_{s,int} + \kappa \cdot d_s \quad (2.15)$$

^b Figure 2.6 is also used in chapters 3, 4, and 5.

where $\varepsilon_{s,int}$ denotes the strain at the intrados strain gauge and ε_{int} denotes the strain at the intrados edge fiber, as shown in Figure 1.7. To convert the strain into stress, Eq. 2.16 is used with a concrete elastic modulus of about 35 GPa (correlating to a concrete strength of 55 MPa).

$$\sigma = -\varepsilon \cdot E_{concrete} \quad (2.16)$$

The expression for stress at the fiber in which the measurement was made is negative to have compressive stresses positive (Figure 1.6d), as is common practice in the geotechnical field. In order to find the lining thrust force F and the bending moment M , expressions 2.17 and 2.18 are used:

$$F = A \frac{\sigma_{ext} + \sigma_{int}}{2} \quad (2.17)$$

$$M = \frac{I_g}{y} \left(\frac{F}{A} - \sigma_{int} \right) = W \left(\sigma_{ext} - \frac{F}{A} \right) \quad (2.18)$$

Where I_g is the segment moment of inertia, and $y = h/2$.

Figure 1.7. Assumed strain and stress distribution in the segment cross-section with installed strain gauges

Out of 17 cross-passage locations, the data from 8 locations could not be used, as continuous strain readings were not collected from both intrados and extrados strain gauges (i.e., thrust force and bending moment could not be calculated) or the location of the strain gauge was not recorded (i.e., it could not be determined if the bending moments were positive or negative). The data collected at the remaining locations was not always continuous, and only at two locations data was collected during cross-passage construction.

All strain gauge data collected can be seen in Appendix C. Figure 1.8 shows an example of strain gauge data collected from one ring at cross-passage-35. Here, continuous data was collected from only two sets of strain gauges, marked in the right side of the figure by the blue and green segments. From the third segment, data from only one strain gauge was collected and for only a short period, rendering the data

unusable. For this location, data from all strain gauges was not collected during cross-passage excavation.

Figure 1.8. Strain vs. time in days of ring 1364 located at cross-passage-35. On the right is the color legend for the position of each strain gauge data set.

Convergence monitoring was performed in both running tunnels at the cross-passage openings and inside the cross-passages. Three cross-sections in each running tunnel at each cross-passage opening were instrumented (see Figure 1.9). In each cross-section, five optical reflective targets were installed according to the configuration shown in Figure 1.10. A manual survey was performed on a daily basis, beginning 20 days prior to break-out. Inside each cross-passage, two cross-sections were instrumented in the first one-third of the excavation length and the second one-third of the excavation length. Three targets were installed in each cross-section, one at the crown and two at the spring-line of the cross-passage, as shown in Figure 1.10. The targets were installed in the full initial lining of the top heading approximately 1 m from the face of the excavation. The first measurement (“zero” measured convergence) was taken before advancing to the next round of excavation.

Figure 1.9. Plan view of a typical cross-passage with the locations of convergence monitoring cross-sections marked in red.

Figure 1.10. Convergence monitoring optical target locations. On the left are running tunnel target locations and on the right cross-passage target location.

2.1.

THE INFLUENCE OF FACE AND SHIELD ANNULUS PRESSURE ON TUNNEL LINER LOAD DEVELOPMENT

A paper to be submitted to a journal paper with Dr. Michael A. Mooney, and Dr. Marte Gutierrez as co-authors.

Abstract

Three dimensional (3D) finite-difference analysis simulations together with rare field data from strain gauges installed in segmental lining rings at the Seattle Sound Transit Northgate Link tunnel project are examined to provide a better understanding of segmental liner loading developed during earth pressure balance shield tunneling. A simplified 3D numerical model is presented for pressure balanced mechanized tunneling, where the annulus between the shield and excavated ground is full of pressurized material, simplifying the shield shape, and the modeling of the annular gap. This simplification is based on the assumption that the shield annulus pressure controls the tunnel convergence prior to lining installation. While the presented model simplifies the modeling of the TBM shield, it captures the important components in shield tunneling, including the jointed segmental lining, grout injection pressure, time-dependent grout hardening, and the non-liner soil behavior using the hardening soil constitutive model. The results of this study show that the final lining loads are controlled by the chamber pressure for pressure balance TBMs with pressurized material in the shield annulus. In the case study presented here, pressure drops of the chamber pressure (common in EPB tunneling due to excavation standstill), result in a significant influence on tunnel lining loads.

1.5 Introduction

The estimation of structural liner loads in shield tunneling is influenced by assumptions made when computationally modeling shield-ground interaction and liner installation. One important design assumption pertains to the contact between the TBM shield and the surrounding soil. Due to overcutting of the TBM (i.e., the difference between the excavated diameter and the diameter of the TBM shield), a shield annulus gap exists between the shield skin and the surrounding ground (Nagel & Meschke 2011). While many widely accepted studies assume that the shield is in full contact with the surrounding ground, i.e., that the ground converges onto the shield (Kasper and Meschke, 2006, Do et al., 2013b, Ninic and Meschke 2017, Kavvadas et al., 2017), based on very low surface settlement achieved in current slurry shield and earth pressure balance machines (EPBM) practice, it can be inferred that pressurized material fills the annular gap supporting the excavation (Nagel & Meschke 2011, Mooney et al. 2016, Dias & Bezuijen 2017, Mori 2016). The pressurized material in the annular gap is hydraulically connected to the pressure at the excavation chamber as described in Figure 2.1. Theoretically, the pressure in the shield annulus is governed by the pressure difference between the face, and the grout injected from the tail shield (Nagel & Meschke 2011, Dias and Bezuijen 2017). Mori (2016) analyzed in-situ measured shield pressures of EPBM from the Seattle Northgate Link project to study the pressure of conditioned soil in the shield annulus. Using pressure sensors installed on the bulkhead together with additional locations on the shield exterior, Mori (2016)

found that the pressure along the shield is connected to the pressure at the excavation chamber with very little pressure loss. Mori (2016) also found that the considerably higher tail shield grout pressure did not influence the shield annulus pressure.

Figure 2.1. Schematic view of how the pressurized material fills the annular gap, allowing the pressure at the cutterhead chamber to be connected to the material in the shield annulus and support the excavation.

Several researchers have developed 3D numerical models over the past two decades. Most of these studies incorporated models that do not consider pressurized material in the shield annulus, or concentrated on surface settlement and not lining loads, or were not validated with experimental results or field measurements. Kasper and Meschke (2006) developed a 3D numerical model for shield tunneling that included the closure of the excavation overcut (shield annulus) to full contact with the TBM shield while accounting for the shield taper (conical shape, with a larger diameter at the face). They investigated the influence of face pressure, grout pressure, and taper of the shield, among other factors. They found that higher face pressures led to a smaller stress release in the soil at the cutting face (arching), which led to a slight increase in lining thrust forces. The increase in face pressure also led to a decrease in the difference in lining pressure between the crown/invert and the spring-line resulting in a decrease in bending moment. They also found that higher grouting pressures resulted in higher lining thrust forces for the same reason. Ninic and Meschke (2017), based on the same 3D model, conducted an extensive parametric study, investigating the influence of initial grouting pressure, grouting pressure gradient, and time-dependent grout stiffness. They concluded that the lining loads are significantly controlled by the grouting process, including the time-dependent stiffness and the distribution of grouting pressures. Neither study incorporated field measurements.

Do et al. (2013b) developed a 3D numerical model to investigate the influence of lining joints on tunnel lining forces. They found a variation in bending moments between successive rings in a staggered segmental lining configuration, highlighting the significance of using a full 3D numerical model to obtain an accurate estimation. Do et al. (2013b) also used a shield annulus closure model where the soil comes into full contact with the shield. The results of this study were not compared with lining loads of field measurements. Litsas et al. (2017) investigated the effects of shield annulus pressure as well as the shield annulus size, grout pressure, and ground conditions on surface settlements by means of 3D numerical modeling. The 3D model also included the closure of the shield annulus to full contact with the tapered TBM shield. In addition to the assumption of no pressurized material in the shield annulus, Litsas et al. (2017) investigated the influence of the shield annulus full of pressurized material by applying total pressure to the tunnel boundary (without modeling the pressurized material itself). The influence of two pressure gradient assumptions was investigated and compared with the no-pressure case. They found that for the partially filled shield annulus with a triangular pressure distribution applied at the front one-third and the tail one-third of the shield length (no support pressure at the mid one-third) almost no surface settlement reduction was observed. However, by applying a continuous pressure distribution connecting the face and grout pressures, a reduction of almost 50% in surface settlement compared to the no-pressure case model. Mooney et al. (2016) investigated the influence of slurry face and annulus pressure, and grouting pressure on surface settlements using 3D numerical modeling validated with data from the Queens bored tunnels project. In this study, the TBM shield was not explicitly modeled. Instead, the influence of the TBM was modeled by a boundary pressure at the tunnel face and along the shield annulus. They found that matching the TBM face and annulus pressure to the geostatic stresses at the crown, spring-line or invert, yielded minimal deformations. However, with the slurry vertical pressure gradient differing from the geostatic stresses, some ground deformation will always occur.

In this paper, the influence of face and shield annulus pressure on tunnel lining loads is investigated using 3D numerical modeling and rare segmental lining load data. Combining the advanced structural modeling approach by Do et al. (2013b) and the modeling approach of the shield annulus pressure by Mooney et al. (2016), a simplified 3D numerical model is presented and validated for pressure balanced TBM tunneling. In the proposed model, the excavation is supported by a radial pressure, modeling the shield annulus full of pressurized material simplifying the shield shape, cutterhead overcut, and annular gap behind the shield. EPBM face, shield annulus, and grout injection pressures monitored during construction are also used in this study to investigate the influence on the lining loads. To provide insight into different aspects of ground-structure interaction, data from strain gauges installed in segmental lining rings at the Seattle Sound Transit Northgate Link tunnel project (Frank et al. 2015, and Epel et al. 2019) are analyzed during the final state of geostatic loading and compared to the numerical analysis results.

1.6 Field Measurement

1.6.1 Northgate Link Project

The Northgate Link Extension project includes 5.6 km of twin bored tunnels and 23 cross passages. The tunnels run north from the University of Washington to Maple Leaf Portal in north Seattle (Epel et al. 2018a, b). The twin bored tunnels were constructed using two EPBM with an excavation diameter of 6.64 m and a shield diameter of 6.44 m. The resulting 100 mm annular shield gap is considerable and larger than the vast majority of shield gaps that are typically on the order of 15-30 mm. The two tunnels were constructed with a center to center distance of about 2 diameters. The tunnels were supported with a single pass, gasketed segmental lining, 25 cm thick, and an extrados diameter of 6.25 m. Each ring is comprised of four full-size segments and key and counter key segments with a nominal width of 1.5 m, and a universal ring concept having an overall ring taper of 69.9 mm. The segment design concrete strength was 55 MPa; the segments were reinforced with wire mesh with primary D14 reinforcement bars.

The geology of the area through which the tunnels were constructed consists of complex and highly variable interlayered glacial and non-glacial soil deposits. As part of the geotechnical baseline report, the geological units were grouped into engineering soil units (ESU) based on their behavioral characteristics. All tunnel excavation was done in the following glacially overridden ESUs: till and till-like deposits (TLD), cohesionless sand and gravel (CSG), cohesionless silt and fine sand (CSF) and cohesive clays and silts (CCS). Figure 2.2 shows geological conditions at the cross-section discussed in this paper with the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) category of each ESU.

Figure 2.2. Northgate Link geological conditions of the cross-section discussed in this paper, located at station 1335+00

1.6.2 Instrumentation and Monitoring

As part of the monitoring program, foil strain gauges with full Wheatstone bridge and connected by wireless RFID transmission were installed in select pre-cast concrete segments. Data from one location/cross-section is presented in this paper. Within each selected ring, three segments were instrumented – two full-size segments plus a key or counter key. Each instrumented segment was outfitted with a set of two foil strain gauges welded to the reinforcement cage, one at the intrados, and one at the extrados, as shown in Figure 2.3. Collection of the strain gauges readings required passing a flat panel RFID reading unit within 30 cm of the concrete surface in the vicinity of the embedded sensor. The monitoring schedule included an initial zero strain reading after the welding of the sister bars prior to casting, followed by readings every two weeks after segment installation.

The orientations of the strain gauges allowed measurement of the circumferential strain and interpretation of the stress developed in the pre-cast segments. With known geometry and strain gauge depth, the measurements collected from a set of two strain gauges allowed for the estimation of both thrust force (hoop force) and bending moment. The sign conventions used convey positive values for compressive thrust force and positive for bending moment when the segment intrados is in tension (Figure 2.3d). In the discussed cross-section, only two rings were instrumented at the second (SB) tunnel excavated, referred to from this point forward as ring A and ring B with one ring in between the two instrumented rings.

Figure 2.3. a) Cross-section of a typical instrumented ring, with the instrumented segments marked A, B & C. b) Segment cross-section at strain gauge location (dimensions in mm). c) Strain gauge location on a typical segment plan view d) Sign convention for bending moments and thrust force.

1.6.3 Shield Annulus Pressure

Figure 2.4 shows the pressure connectivity between the chamber and the shield annulus in the first tunnel (shield pressures were only monitored in the first tunnel excavated). The figure shows the pressure measured during the installation of rings 1360-1368 located at the same cross-section of the instrumented rings in the second tunnel. The average difference between the upper chamber (sensor p_6 Figure 2.5) and the top tail shield sensor (sensor P_{tail11} Figure 2.5) (corrected to the elevation of the chamber top sensor) at the first tunnel is approximately 5%. Table 2.1 shows the average pressures (over six rings prior to the installation of ring B) monitored during the excavation of both tunnels. When put in the context of the effective stress at spring-line depth, after balancing the water pressure, the effective support pressure p'_i is approximately 0.13 and 0.10 of the effective vertical earth pressure σ'_v for the first and second tunnels respectively (with $\sigma'_v = 660$ kPa and the hydrostatic water pressure is 60 kPa). The shield pressures are adjusted to the elevation of the top and bottom chamber pressure sensors (Figure 2.5) by linear interpolation using a data-determined pressure gradient. In ideal EPBM construction, the support pressure is maintained relatively constant with gradual changes required as ground conditions change. The first support pressure assumption considered in this study is a constant face and shield annulus pressure, where the value of the face and shield annulus pressure does not change as the TBM advances. For the constant pressure case assumed in the numerical analysis discussed in section 2.4, the spring-line chamber pressures presented in Table 2.1 are used.

Figure 2.4. Chamber and shield pressure vs. time at the NB tunnel (first tunnel excavated) during the installation of rings 1360-1368 located at the same cross-section of the instrumented rings installed in the second tunnel. The schematic of the TBM is shown on the plot with the locations of the pressure sensors and the corresponding color. Shield annulus pressures are adjusted to the elevation of chamber pressure sensor P_6 according to a measured chamber pressure gradient of 14 kN/m^3 .

Figure 2.5. Bulkhead pressure sensors, shield pressure sensors, and grout injection locations on the NB TBM (first tunnel excavated); dimensions in m (from Mori 2016).

Table 2.1. TBM parameters monitored in both NB TBM (first tunnel excavated) and SB TBM (second tunnel excavated). The values represent the measurements during the excavation of the six rings prior to the installation of ring B. For the NB tunnel, the values represent the measurements of the parallel section.

TBM parameter	Unit	(1) NB TBM		(2) SB TBM	
		Average	Standard deviation	Average	Standard deviation
Total thrust force	MN	20.5	1.6	15.8	1.1
Crown chamber pressure	kPa	90	9	75	8
Spring-line chamber pressure	kPa	131	10	110	7
Invert chamber pressure	kPa	155	15	137	7
P _{front11}	kPa	92	5	NA	NA
P _{front5}	kPa	90	6	NA	NA
P _{tail11}	kPa	86	6	NA	NA
P _{tail5}	kPa	130	6	NA	NA
Grout injection pressure 1 ^c	kPa	200	5	305	35
Grout injection pressure 2 ^c	kPa	200	7	480	100
Grout injection pressure 3 ^c	kPa	200	15	246	100

* σ'_v at spring-line is 660 kPa and the water pressure is 60 kPa

NA- Not available – no shield pressures were measured at the SB TBM

^c Grout injection pressures are measured in the injection line approximately 4 m upstream from injection point

1.7 Numerical Model Description

The 3D numerical model was developed using the commercial software package FLAC3D (Itasca 2009), based on a generalized finite difference method (FDM). After a study of the boundary effects and mesh discretization, the 3D model dimensions were set to 124 m wide, 120 m long, and a height of 70 m. To avoid the influence of boundary conditions, lining loads results were taken at a distance of about 4D from the boundary (monitoring section in Figure 2.6); beyond the 5D distance, boundary conditions were found to be negligible. The simulation of each tunnel excavation extended to a distance of more than 5D past the monitored rings presented in Figures 3.14-3.19, as the influence of the face is negligible at a distance of more than 2.5D (section 2.4).

Figure 2.6. FLAC3D model general configuration and location of the monitoring section chosen for result analysis.

1.7.1 Modeling the Tunneling Process

The 3D numerical model is based on the work of Mooney et al. (2016) and Do et al. (2013a, b, and c), simulating the different activities of the shield tunneling process with a simplification of the shield by applying the shield annulus pressure. This simplification is based on the assumption that the shield annulus pressure controls the tunnel convergence prior to lining installation, i.e., that the excavated ground does not automatically converge onto the shield. This assumption must be validated by demonstrating that the maximum tunnel displacement is smaller than the annulus gap. For the analyzed case discussed in this paper, this is shown in section 2.4. The different activities included in the proposed model include: the pressurized face by slurry or earth pressure balance, pressurized annulus around the machine shield, installation of the pre-cast segmental lining at the shield tail, incorporation of segmental lining longitudinal and circumferential joint behavior, and the time-dependent annulus grout between the lining extrados and the soil. A multi-stage step by step procedure has been implemented using the following sequence (Figure 2.7):

- Initial geostatic conditions with a lateral earth pressure ratio of $K_0=0.6$ are applied.

- At each excavation stage, the modeled excavation advances by removing one excavation length (ring length n in Figure 2.7) equal to the width of one segmental ring (1.5 m).
- A total muck pressure is applied normal to the tunnel face and excavation boundary. An assumption is made that the cutterhead applies insignificant force/pressure to the face, i.e., that the chamber pressure provides all of the face support pressure.
- The shield annulus pressure is uniformly distributed along the 9 m length of the TBM shield (6 advance lengths) up to the last ring length where the pressure connectivity between the annulus grout and the shield annulus pressure is assumed to be linear (e.g., the shield is not modeled).
- At a distance of 10.5 m (7 advance lengths) behind the face (ring length $n-7$ in Figure 2.7), the segmental lining is installed in the model along with an annulus of grout material between the lining and the partially-converged ground. Grouting pressure is applied normal to the lining and ground along the last ring installed.
- One ring behind the current ring installed (ring $n-8$ in Figure 2.7), groundwater pressure is applied to the lining, and the grout stiffness increases according to a time-dependent modulus increase (detailed in section 2.3.4).

Figure 2.7. Step by step simulation procedure of pressure balance TBM tunneling

1.7.2 Modeling Face and Shield Annulus Pressure

The face pressure is assumed to vary linearly with depth according to a pressure gradient determined from pressure sensors and is modeled by a pressure distribution normal to the tunnel face. The shield annulus pressure is modeled by applying a normal pressure to the cylindrical excavation surface from the tunnel face to the tail shield. This shield annulus pressure also varies linearly with depth, corresponding to the value of the face pressure at the same elevation. Based on the pressure connectivity observed in Figure 2.4 with a very low average pressure difference between the chamber pressure and the tail shield pressure, the modeled shield annulus pressure is uniformly

distributed along the shield length up to the last excavation length (1.5 m) where the pressure connectivity between the annulus grout and the shield annulus pressure is assumed to be linear (Figure 2.7). The uniform pressure along the shield length may be a result of the 100 mm shield gap and may be unique to this project. Varying pressure distributions along the shield reported by Bezuijen and Bakker (2008) could be modeled if warranted. The modeled face and shield annulus pressure value does not change as the TBM advances. These modeled face and shield annulus pressures are prescribed a value of 130 kPa for the first tunnel and 110 kPa for the second tunnel at spring-line level, determined from the average monitored pressure during excavation at spring-line (excluding standstill) and summarized in Table 2.1. The pressure is applied normal to the face of each soil element as total stress.

1.7.3 Modeling the Tunnel Lining

Following Do et al. (2013b), the segmental lining is modeled by linear-elastic embedded liner elements (Itasca 2009). This embedded liner element is a shell element with two links at each node, permitting the interaction between the host medium (ground) and the structural element at both sides of the element. One side of the embedded liner element is connected to the surrounding ground, and the other end is manipulated to connect the two adjacent segments (Figure 2.8a). Every link includes six degrees of freedom, and each degree of freedom can be assigned one of three boundary conditions: free, rigid, and deformable. The boundary conditions are represented by six springs, with three translational components (K_R and K_A in Figure 2.8b) and three rotational components (K_θ in Figure 2.8b).

In this study, a deformable rotational stiffness is prescribed around the axis of the longitudinal joint ($K_{\theta_{xx}}$) by a bi-linear relation as used by Thienert and Pulsfort (2011), Do et al. (2013a, b) and others. The attachment conditions of all translational components ($K_{A_{xx}}$, $K_{A_{yy}}$, and $K_{R_{zz}}$) and the two remaining rotational components ($K_{\theta_{zz}}$ and $K_{\theta_{yy}}$) are assumed to be rigid (Do et al. 2013a, b). The circumferential joint coupling is modeled by shear deformable springs in the radial direction ($K_{R_{zz}}$) to carry the shear force that results from the displacement difference in the radial direction between two adjacent rings (Blom 2003, Kavvada 2017, Arnau and Molins 2011). For more detail on the joint rotational stiffness, refer to Thienert and Pulsfort (2011), and Do et al. (2013a, b).

For the liner-soil interface, only two extreme interface conditions are usually assumed for analytical solutions (Rankin et al. 1978): full-slip with no transfer of tangential stress between the liner and the ground/grout, and no-slip conditions allowing the transfer of the shear tangential stress between the liner and the ground/grout. In numerical ground-structure interaction analysis, the interface can also be modeled with frictional contact. Zero coefficient of friction in which no tangential shear stress is transferred between the lining and the ground is analogous to the full slip condition (Sedarat et al. 2009). With the smooth finished surface of the pre-cast lining segments, the shear failure criterion between the lining and the annulus grout can be assumed closer to full-slip with low friction and zero cohesion. In this study, the lining-grout interface conditions are assumed as partial-slip with a friction angle of 5° , allowing some transfer of tangential stress between the liner and the grout. The frictional contact model

has a linear-elastic link between the soil and the liner for shear stresses lower than the allowable shear strength described by the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion. This linear-elastic link (marked (1) in Figure 2.8a) allows for sliding and opening relative to the surrounding ground and was given a stiffness using a widely expected rule of thumb (Itasca 2009, Do et al. 2013a, b) in which k_n (the normal stiffness) and k_s (tangential stiffness) are set to one hundred times the equivalent stiffness of the neighboring zone (surrounding ground). The interface between the grout and the soil is assumed to be connected rigidly due to the very rough surface.

Figure 2.8. Segmental lining modeling concept (a) node connectivity concept (after Do et al. 2013a), (b) K_R , K_A , K_θ stiffness in the axial, radial and rotational directions of a ring joint (Do et al. 2013a)

1.7.4 Annulus Grout

Two-component grout was used to fill the annular gap in the Northgate Link project. The two-component grout is injected behind the tunnel lining while the TBM is advancing and gels in less than a minute (Arash et al. 2018). As the grout continues to set with time, its elastic modulus and strength increase while the initial fluid pressure of the grout dissipates. The grout mix design achieved an average compressive strength of 1.7 MPa in 28 days, correlating to an elastic modulus of 350 MPa according to Flores (2015). The time-dependent grout behavior is modeled by a gradual elastic modulus increase as the excavation advances. Accounting for the actual TBM advance rate of 19 rings per day of the second tunnel (28.5 m advance per day) on the day the monitored rings were installed, the grout stiffness is increased every excavation stage to simulate the time-dependent hardening process. The grout hardening function adopted is based on the time-dependent relation proposed by Meschke et al. (1996), and is widely used for simulating the time-dependent hardening of grout in tunnel modeling, e.g., Kasper and Meschke (2004); Kavvadas et al. (2017); Do et al. (2014). With no literature known by the authors on the early life (under 7 hours) stiffness of two-component grout, an initial grout modulus of 10 MPa is used for the last ring installed (ring n-7) correlating to a three-hour grout stiffness. The grout modulus at ring n-8 is assumed to be the 8-hour

stiffness due to the fast setting time of two-component grout, followed by the adopted time-dependent relation according to the actual TBM advance rate noted above (Figure 2.9). For each ring length, the grout stiffness is constant during every analysis step. The mix design consisted of fly ash replacement greater than 50%. Flores (2015) found that grout with 50% fly ash replacement has a 92-day stiffness five times greater than 28-day stiffness. To account for the fly-ash replacement influence, the first tunnel grout stiffness is increased to the 92-day stiffness of 1750 MPa prior to the simulation of the second tunnel excavation, as the second (SB) TBM passed the monitored section four months after the first TBM (NB).

In the proposed model, the grout is modeled by 3D solid elements between the excavation boundary and the concrete lining shell elements. The grout pressure was modeled by a gravitationally controlled distributed load, applied both on the excavation boundary and on the n-7 ring segment (Figure 2.7). As the grout sets quickly, the pressure is assumed to dissipate within the stage cycle of ring installation and hence is applied only along the last ring installed (1.5 m as shown in Figure 2.7). The grout injection pressures were monitored during excavation and are shown in Table 2.1. The grout pressure used in the 3D model at the first tunnel is 200 kPa and 350 kPa at the second tunnel, based on and the average (from the three injection ports) measured injection pressure. The grout pressure value used for this analysis is assumed to be equal to the injection pressure as found by Hashimoto et al. (2004).

Figure 2.9. Development of grout elastic modulus with time. (a) Development of the grout elastic modulus by hours. (b) The development of the grout elastic modulus up to the 28-day strength of 350 MPa.

1.7.5 Soil Constitutive Model

In this study, the hardening soil small-strains (HSS) model (referred to by Itasca 2009 as the plastic-hardening small strains) is used. Based on the work of Schanz (1999) and Benz (2006), the HSS model is characterized by a frictional Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, stress-dependent soil stiffness, and different unloading/reloading stiffness compared to the virgin loading. For the simulation of mechanized tunneling, the use of a non-linear constitutive model such as the HSS model has significant importance as the near field zone is subjected initially to an unloading stress path with unloading-reloading cycles, due to changing confinement conditions from tunnel

excavation, chamber/shield pressure changes, and grouting pressure (Arash et al. 2018, Do et al. 2013c).

The HSS model parameters were determined from the results of available triaxial tests and pressuremeter tests (Soundtransit, 2013a), and are presented in Table 2.2. Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show the fit between the lab/field tests and the numerical tests using the HSS model parameters for the CSG soil. The strain range observed in the analysis discussed in section 2.4 is on the order of 1%. Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show that the calibrated HSS model parameters give good agreement with the lab and field tests within the range of 1% strain. Figure 2.10 shows the deviator stress vs. axial strain and volumetric strain vs. axial strain of the consolidated drained triaxial laboratory tests and the numerical test using the HSS model properties in Table 2.2. In the case of the deviator stress vs. axial strain, the HSS model models the CSG response well, and the volumetric strain is modeled reasonably well. Figure 2.11 shows the radial pressuremeter pressure vs. radial strain from the field pressuremeter test conducted at the vicinity of the analyzed tunnel cross-section and the numerical pressuremeter test using the HSS model properties in Table 2.2. During virgin loading, the HSS model predicts the field test reasonably well within the range of 1% radial strain. The unloading reloading response is also predicted reasonably well for the first three increments. With the tunnel excavated through the highly permeable CSG material, all calculations have been performed under drained conditions, accounting for a lateral earth pressure coefficient, $K_0=0.6$.

Table 2.2. Input parameters of the HSS constitutive model.

Description	Symbol	Unit	CSG
Internal friction angle	ϕ'	°	41
Dilation angle	ψ'	°	9
Cohesion	c'	kPa	0
Secant stiffness in triaxial test	E^{ref}_{50}	MPa	55
Tangent stiffness in oedometer test	E^{ref}_{oed}	MPa	55
Unloading-reloading stiffness	E^{ref}_{ur}	MPa	140
Small-strain stiffness	E^{ref}_0	MPa	240
Poisson's ratio	ν	-	0.2
Exponent power	m	-	0.68
Reference stress	p^{ref}	kPa	100
Failure ratio	R_f	-	0.85

Figure 2.10. (a) The volumetric-strain vs axial-strain, and (b) stress vs strain curve from a drained triaxial compression test (lab data) and numerical model drained triaxial compression test using the HSS properties for the CSG soil unit.

Figure 2.11. Stress-Strain Curve of a field pressuremeter test (PMT) and the numerical model pressuremeter simulation using the HSS properties for the CSG soil unit.

1.8 Results

The proposed model (Section 2.3) was used to investigate the influence of face and shield annulus pressure on tunnel lining loads. Figures 3.12-3.17 present results from the constant pressure case, where a constant face and annulus pressure (i.e., no change in pressure between ring advances) is applied at each tunnel with a value of 130 kPa for the first tunnel and 110 kPa for the second tunnel at the spring-line level as summarized in Table 2.1.

Figure 2.12 shows the model-produced longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) at the excavated ground crown and invert after the excavation and lining installation of the first and second tunnels. The displacements at the excavated ground crown reach a constant value (convergence) at a distance of about 2.5D from the face. Higher displacements are predicted in the second tunnel (31 mm) compared to the first tunnel (24 mm) due to the lower face and annular pressure during the excavation of the

second tunnel. The unlined LDP at the first tunnel crown, determined by the 3D numerical model with applied EPBM pressures, illustrates that considerable convergence occurs prior to lining installation. The spring-line LDP (not shown here) has a similar shape to the crown LDP with a lower displacement of 16 mm for the first tunnel and 20 mm for the second tunnel, given the lower horizontal geostatic stress ($K_0 = 0.6$). The magnitude of observed convergence supports the modeling assumption that the ground does not converge on to the TBM shield as the annulus gap is 100 mm.

Given the stress-dependent stiffness of the HSS model together with the increases in effective stress with depth, the convergence at the tunnel crown is significantly higher compared to the invert convergence (uplift), with a stiffer response of the ground underlying the tunnel invert. The non-linear stress-strain relationship of the HSS model results in a lower relative difference in displacements between the inverts of the first and second tunnels (15% lower at the first tunnel) compared to the crown displacements (23% lower at the first tunnel).

The influence of the grouting pressure on tunnel deformation at the tail shield is more prominent at the second tunnel with a grouting pressure of 350 kPa compared to 200 kPa in the first tunnel. With a significantly higher grouting pressure compared to shield annulus pressure, a reduction in ground deformation is observed at the tail shield of the second tunnel (10.5 m behind the face). This small reduction in deformation can be attributed to the considerable irreversible plastic deformation as well as the different primary loading stiffness and reloading stiffness of the HSS model, while the use of an elastic-perfectly-plastic soil model would result in an unrealistically large reduction in convergence as discussed by Mollon et al. (2013), and Kavvadas et al. (2017). After the grout pressure dissipates (grout pressure applied only to the first installed ring), an increase in ground deformation occurs at ring n-8 (12 m behind the face).

Figure 2.12. Longitudinal displacement profile (ground deformations) at the first lined tunnel (solid lines) and second lined tunnel (dashed lines) crown and invert. The LDP of the first unlined tunnel crown is shown by the dotted line. The tunnel face is at X=0, and the first lining ring is at X=10.5 m.

Consistent with convergence behavior, the stress redistribution around the tunnels reaches a constant state at a distance of 2.5D from the face. Figure 2.13a shows the minimum principal stress field (minimum compressive stress) at X=30 m after completion of the first tunnel. Figure 2.13a also shows the principal stress trajectories (black crosses) where the maximum principal stress is tangent to the tunnel boundary illustrating stress redistribution/flow around the opening both vertically and horizontally. With only the EPBM support pressure supporting the tunnel excavation prior to the installation of the tunnel lining, the radial stress (minimum principal stress in Figure 2.13a) is equal to the relatively low EPBM support pressure ($p'_i/\sigma'_v = 0.13$). After the pre-cast segmental lining is installed in the first tunnel, the lining provides confinement to the surrounding ground, allowing higher radial stress to develop around the tunnel. As the second tunnel is excavated, the deconfinement of the soil around the second tunnel results in a decrease in radial stresses around it (Figure 2.13b), and redistribution of the stress around the supported first tunnel. The greatest increase in radial stresses occurs at the side closer to the second tunnel. This redistribution of stresses around the first tunnel illustrates the impact the second tunnel has on the first tunnel lining loads, as will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 2.13. Minimum principal effective stress (minimum compression) contour at X=30 m (a) after the excavation of the first tunnel and (b) after the excavation of the second tunnel. The principal stress trajectories are shown by black crosses. The longer lines indicate the direction of the maximum principal stress, and the shorter lines indicate the minimum principal stress. Geostatic effective vertical stress at spring-line is about 660 kPa, and the effective horizontal stress is about 370 kPa.

1.8.1 Liner Load Development in the First Tunnel

Figures 3.14a and 3.14b show the model-estimated load development within a single ring in the first tunnel for constant face and shield annulus pressure of 130 kPa at the spring-line. There were no field measurements of liner loads in the first tunnel. Model-estimated first tunnel liner loading is presented after the completion of the first tunnel and after the completion of the second tunnel. Figure 2.14a shows the development of liner bending moments where, after the completion of the excavation and support of the first tunnel, a vertically symmetric low magnitude bending moment diagram is observed with a maximum positive bending moment of 4 kN-m at invert and a maximum negative bending moment of 3 kN-m at spring-line. This squatting behavior is consistent with a lateral earth pressure ratio lower the unity ($K_o = 0.6$) also observed in Figure 2.15a showing the lining deformations after the completion of the first tunnel (in red). Following the excavation of the second tunnel, an increase in bending moment occurs in the first tunnel (Figure 2.14a) with additional squatting of the tunnel lining, as shown by the blue line Figure 15a. This additional squatting is induced by the increase in radial stresses around the supported first tunnel and most significantly at the side closer to the second tunnel, as seen in Figure 2.13. This asymmetric loading condition

results in an asymmetric squatting diagram, deforming the 1 o'clock position inwards. While the spring-line closer to the second tunnel does not deform outward with the increase in radial stress seen in Figure 2.13, the spring-line at the opposite side deforms outwards due to the lower confining radial stress. As mentioned above, with the pre-cast segmental lining supporting the ground around the first tunnel, higher stresses can develop around the tunnel as a result of excavation of the second tunnel and the deconfinement of the soil around the second tunnel. Despite the deconfinement around the second tunnel, Figure 2.15b shows that the excavation of the second tunnel does not impose substantial additional horizontal soil displacement at the first tunnel spring-line. The horizontal displacements resulting from the excavation of the first tunnel (shown by the red line) show convergence towards the first tunnel (negative), and decay within a short distance from the maximum value at the first tunnel excavation boundary ($0.5D$) to less than 10% at the location of the second tunnel spring-line is to be located ($1.3D$). The excavation of the second tunnel imposes a horizontal displacement in the opposite direction (positive displacement implies movement toward the second tunnel) only up to a distance of about $0.5D$ from the second tunnel spring-line ($0.8D$). Figure 14a also shows the moment reduction at the joint locations as a result of the modeled joint rotation stiffness (section 2.3.3).

Figure 2.14. Loads developed in the first tunnel: (a) Bending moment (kN-m/m) and (b) Thrust force (kN/m) diagrams after first tunnel excavation for constant internal support pressure of 130 kPa.

Figure 2.15. (a) Radial lining displacements of the first tunnel lining after the completion of the first tunnel in red, and in blue is the displacements after the completion of the second tunnel. Negative displacements are inwards. (b) Horizontal soil displacements at the spring-line level vs. the distance from the first tunnel center in terms of D . Displacements resulting from the excavation of the first tunnel are shown by the blue line, and the red line shows the displacement resulting from the second tunnel excavation. The direction of the deformations is shown in the center top of the figure.

Figure 2.14b shows a considerable increase in thrust force as a result of the excavation of the second tunnel with a low face and shield annulus pressure relative to the field stresses $p'_i/\sigma'_v = 0.13$ (after balancing the water pressure). This increase in thrust force is slightly higher at the side closer to the second tunnel as a result of the higher increase in radial stresses on that side. While the 80% increase in thrust force at the tunnel spring-line might be overestimated due to the HSS stress dependent stiffness behavior, it should also be pointed out that the face and shield annulus pressure used during the excavation of the second tunnel is very low in terms of p'_i/σ'_v . Figure 2.16 shows that by increasing the face and shield annulus pressure at the second tunnel to 200 and 300 kPa ($p'_i/\sigma'_v = 0.2$ and 0.35), the increase in lining forces drops to about 55% and 40% respectively. These values are more consistent with the 40% increase in thrust force found by Do et al. (2014d), due to the excavation of a parallel tunnel.

Figure 2.16. Thrust force (kN/m) diagram for different face and shield annulus pressures modeled during the second tunnel excavation

1.8.2 Load Development in Second Tunnel

Figures 3.17a and 3.17b show the comparison between the second tunnel liner loads estimated from the strain measurements and the numerical analysis results for constant internal support pressure of 110 kPa at spring-line. Ring A and ring B in the numerical model are installed with one ring between them to simulate the positions of the instrumented rings installed in the Northgate Link project with the same joint orientation as installed in the field. The 3D numerical model results shown in Figure 2.17b provide a bending moment response consistent with squatting lining behavior as expected in $K_0 = 0.6$ conditions, and as seen for the first tunnel. Despite the lower EPB support pressure in the second tunnel, both bending moments and thrust forces are slightly higher in the second tunnel compared to the first tunnel (before the excavation of the second tunnel) as a result of the higher grouting pressure of 350 kPa and 200 kPa respectively. This is consistent with the findings of Ninic and Meschke (2017) who found that an increase from 150 kPa to 300 kPa in grout pressure resulted in a 50% increase in thrust force. While the excavation of the second tunnel had a considerable influence on the first tunnel, the existence of the first tunnel prior to the construction of the second tunnel does not appear to have an impact on the second tunnel.

With the field measured lining loads shown separately for ring A in blue, and in red for ring B, Figure 2.17b shows a difference between thrust force of ring A and ring B. Despite being located at the crown and spring-line, and a K_0 loading of 0.6, the ring A measured thrust forces have a difference of only 6%. The measured thrust forces in ring B also have a difference of only 3%, however, this is somewhat expected with both located between the crown and spring-line on opposite sides. Ring A thrust force was measured to be about 25-30% greater than ring B thrust force, despite only having one ring between them. Unlike with the measured thrust force, the bending moments in

Figure 2.17a do not show different magnitudes at each ring. However, while Figure 2.17a shows that the measured bending moments show a squatting behavior expected in $K_0 = 0.6$ conditions, the 1 o'clock position and the 2 o'clock positions show considerably higher moments compared to the 9 and 10 o'clock measurements.

Figure 2.17. Loads developed in the second tunnel (located on the right to the first tunnel): (a) bending moment (kN-m/m) and (b) thrust force (kN/m) diagrams after second tunnel excavation for constant internal support pressure of 110 kPa.

The 3D computational model results reasonably match two of the four measured bending moments. For each ring, only one of the two bending moment measurements reasonably matches the 3D numerical model results, while the other measurement is significantly higher. The modeled ring B thrust force prediction is within 8-12% of measured, while the ring A measured thrust force is significantly higher than modeled. We hypothesize that the difference in thrust force between ring A and ring B can be explained by both the chamber pressure decrease that occurred during standstill and a decrease of about 10 kPa in average support pressure after ring A is installed, as shown in Figure 2.18. Figure 2.18 shows the pressure measured in the excavation chamber of the second tunnel (no shield pressure sensors were installed in the second TBM) during the installation of the two instrumented rings. After ring A is installed, a considerable pressure drop occurs during EPBM standstill, and a second significant pressure drop occurs after ring B is installed. The first pressure drop occurred after ring A is partly exposed from under the shield (average drop of pressure more than 40 kPa during the standstill) (top of Figure 2.18), and two-component grout is injected between

the segment and the ground. Ring B experiences a similar drop in the chamber pressure as described for ring A.

Figure 2.18. Chamber pressure vs. time at the SB TBM (second tunnel excavated) during the installation of the instrumented segments. The blue shaded areas mark the excavation cycle, and the white areas mark the standstill due to ring build. The three pressure measurements show the average pressure measured at the top, center, and bottom of the chamber (location of the sensors can be seen at the top right with the corresponding color). When rings A and B are partially exposed from under the shield (as illustrated at the top of the figure), a drop in chamber pressure can be observed.

A numerical simulation incorporating the recorded pressure drops was conducted to investigate this observation. In this simulation, two pressure drops were simulated after the installation of the monitored rings, as measured during excavation (Figure 2.18). Each pressure drop was modeled by introducing an additional stage between excavation steps. After the installation of the monitored ring, the face and shield pressure decreased uniformly by 40 kPa. The face and shield annulus are then increased to the average value of support pressure after the pressure drop (100 kPa) before the step by step excavation continues with this support pressure of 100 kPa.

Figure 2.19b shows the thrust force developed in the two monitored rings as a result of the pressure drop simulation. The forces estimated by the numerical analysis provide an accurate prediction of the thrust forces measured in rings A and B. Accounting for the pressure drop, the predicted thrust force at the crown of ring A is about 25% higher compared to ring B and about 45% higher than predicted in the constant pressure case. For a better understanding of how the pressure drop influenced the lining loads, Figure 2.20 shows how the first drop of the face and shield annulus pressure (after ring A is installed) results in the redistribution of the stresses around the opening. Having ring A supporting the ground immediately behind the tail shield, some of the redistributed stresses are taken by ring A, resulting in an increase of about 30-45% in thrust relative to the constant pressure case (Figure 2.19b dashed gray line). This can be seen in Figure 2.20 by the increase in vertical effective stress above ring A

after the pressure drop. After the excavation continues, ring B is installed, supporting the ground that experienced a higher degree of relaxation compared to the constant pressure case (Figure 2.20b). With lower face and shield annulus pressure resulting in a higher degree of relaxation, lower thrust forces are expected in ring B. However after ring B is installed, the second pressure drop occurs, resulting in an increase in stresses around the installed ring, loading ring B in the same manner as seen for ring A and described above. This results in a lower thrust force in ring B by about 25-30% compared to ring A, yet higher by about 12% compared to the constant pressure case. Despite the noticeable impact the pressure drops have on the thrust forces, Figure 2.19a shows little change in the bending forces compared to the constant pressure case. This can be explained by the observation that the pressure drop results in a uniform radial increase in stress around the monitored rings resulting in only an increase in thrust force and a small change in bending moments (equivocal to an increase in a hydrostatic load). The two bending moment measurements higher than predicted could not be fitted and could be explained by a local influence not captured in this model.

Figure 2.19. Loads developed as a result of the chamber pressure drop in the two monitored rings in the second tunnel (SB), (a) bending moment (kN-m/m) and (b) thrust force (kN/m)

Figure 2.20. Vertical effective stress contour of the second tunnel (a) before the pressure drop after ring A installation (b) after pressure drop after ring A installation

1.9 Conclusions

Segmental tunnel lining load development during EPBM shield tunneling was studied using 3D numerical modeling and rare field data of measured thrust forces and bending moments from the Northgate Link project in Seattle. The advanced 3D numerical model developed for pressure balanced mechanized tunneling, simulates the face and shield annulus pressure, advanced hardening soil behavior, installation of jointed segmental lining rings, grout injection pressure, and time-dependent grout hardening. Validation of the proposed model and the assumptions taken were obtained by very good agreement between the field data of measured loads and the loads estimated by the model.

From this study, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Drops of the chamber pressure that are common in EPBM tunneling due to excavation standstill result in a significant influence on tunnel lining thrust force. As a result of the pressure drop at the chamber and the shield annulus, the stress redistributes, decreasing around the shield and increasing around the last installed rings (closest to the shield tail). This results in an increase in the lining thrust force of the last installed rings with the highest increase in the last ring installed and reducing farther away behind the tail. The rings installed supporting the ground that experienced the pressure drop will develop lower lining loads due to the higher degree of relaxation as a result of the pressure drop.

- For pressure balance TBMs with the flow of pressurized material (e.g., conditioned soil or slurry) behind the shield into the shield annulus, the final lining loads are controlled by the chamber pressure, as seen when incorporating the pressure drops. The proposed model simplifying the TBM shield with the shield annulus pressure can be used to predict the segmental lining structural forces without the need for complex modeling of the shield and soil-shield interaction.
- Based on the importance of the TBM support pressure for the prediction of lining load, the ability to predict the amount of convergence prior to lining installation relies on the correct support pressure applied during excavation and is critical for tunnel lining structural calculations in pressure balance TBM tunneling.
- The excavation of the second tunnel for the conditions described in this study result in a significant increase of bending moments and thrust forces in the first tunnel lining. By increasing the face and shield annulus pressure in the second tunnel, the increase in lining loads in the first tunnel is reduced. The lining loads in the second tunnel do not seem to be higher than that of a single tunnel.

3.1.

HARDENING-SOIL-SMALL-STRAIN LONGITUDINAL DISPLACEMENT BEHAVIOR IN SOFT GROUND TUNNELING

A paper to be submitted to a journal paper with Dr. Michael A. Mooney, and Dr. Marte Gutierrez as co-authors.

Abstract

The hardening soil small-strain (HSS) model is widely used in soft ground tunnel analysis in the last decade, given the ability of this advanced soil model to generate more realistic soil response in terms of non-linearity, stress dependency, and inelasticity. The use of this non-linear constitutive model in pressure balance TBM tunneling has significant importance as the near field zone is subjected mostly to an unloading stress path with the change in confinement conditions from tunnel excavation, and chamber pressure. This paper investigates the ground response of a tunnel excavated in HSS ground and proposes a new longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) solution for HSS soft ground for application in pressure balance TBM tunneling. The results of this paper show that the LDP predicted when using the Mohr-Coulomb elastic-perfectly plastic model can overestimate pre-convergence by 20% compared to the HSS model. The new HSS LDP solution is validated by comprehensive parametric analysis and shows a very good ability to predict the HSS ground response.

1.10 Introduction

The longitudinal displacement profile (LDP) relating the tunnel displacement to the position of the tunnel face and support installation has become a standard analysis tool to bring the longitudinal (3D) effects of ground convergence into 2D transverse plane analysis (Vlachopoulos and Diederichs, 2009, Prassetyo and Gutierrez, 2018). A number of theoretical and empirical LDP relationships have been developed in the past four decades addressing linear-elastic and elastic perfectly-plastic (EPP) material behavior for tunnels constructed using conventional excavation methods and open mode TBMs. Panet and Guenot (1982), Panet (1995), and Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) published LDP equations considering linear-elastic material under isotropic stresses for an unsupported tunnel in drained conditions. Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) extended the LDP relation to elastic perfectly-plastic material, valid for the elastic case through large plastic zone development.

Soil is well-known to behave non-linearly under different stress and strain conditions. The hardening soil-small strain (HSS) (Schanz et al., 1999, and Benz, 2006) is an advanced non-linear elastoplastic constitutive model that can better simulate real soil/rock behavior, and is widely used in soft ground tunnel analysis (Teo and Wong 2012, Do et al. 2013, Zhao et al. 2017, Arash et al. 2018, and others). The HSS model can reproduce soil behavior more accurately than linear-elastic and EEP soil models such as the Mohr-Coulomb model (MC) by including features such as hyperbolic stress-strain relationship in axial drained compression, plastic strain in mobilizing friction, plastic strain in primary compression (virgin compression loading), and stress-

dependent stiffness associated to a power law (Arash et al. 2018, Peng et al. 2011, Do et al. 2013c).

No LDP solution in available literature has been developed for an HSS model, and the nature of the HSS model suggests it will have a significant influence on the LDP (the analysis presented in this paper will confirm this). In fact, the use of the linear-elastic and the EPP soil behavioral models can result in the overestimation of convergence that will occur prior to liner installation. This is particularly important for the simulation of pressure balance shield tunneling, where the use of a non-linear constitutive model has significant importance as the near field zone is subjected mostly to an unloading stress path with the change in confinement conditions as well as unloading-reloading cycles from tunnel excavation, chamber pressure, and grouting pressure (Arash et al. 2018, Do et al. 2013).

With the accuracy of the LDP solution critical for a reliable prediction of the lining forces, the objective of the study described in this paper was to investigate the HSS ground response and develop an LDP solution for HSS-modeled soft ground for application to shield tunneling. As most soft ground tunnels are constructed using pressure balance TBMs (slurry or EPB), this LDP solution is developed to account for different TBM support pressures. 3D and axisymmetric numerical models are used in this study to develop the HSS LDP solution for soft ground characterized by the HSS model. A comprehensive parametric analysis is conducted to investigate the influence of different degrees of elastoplastic behavior and selected input parameters of the HSS model and validate the reliability of the HSS LDP solution.

1.11 Background

1.11.1 Existing Longitudinal Displacement Profiles

The LDP predicts the tunnel radial displacement (u) (or convergence) as a function of the distance from the face (X), where X is negative in front of the face and positive behind the face (Figure 3.1). The maximum displacement happens at a distance behind the tunnel face (approximately 3.5 tunnel radii for the linear-elastic case and further away as the plastic zone increases, according to Vlachopoulos and Diederichs, 2009). A portion of the displacement occurs before the face advances past a specific point (ahead of the face). Typically a normalized displacement ($u^* = u/u_{max}$) is estimated as a function of the normalized distance ($X^* = X/R_0$), where u_{max} is the maximum tunnel radial displacement, i.e., at $X^* \gg R_0$, and R_0 is the tunnel radius.

Figure 3.1. Schematic of the tunnel advance, showing that X is negative in front of the face and positive behind the face.

Various LDP relations have been proposed by different researchers for circular deep tunnels in a non-gravitational isotropic stress field and in isotropic homogeneous ground. Panet and Guenet (1982), and Panet (1993) developed the first LDP equations for the linear elastic case behind the tunnel face that was later revised by Panet (1995):

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = 0.25 + 0.75 \left(1 - \left(\frac{0.75}{0.75+X^*} \right)^2 \right) \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (4.1)$$

This solution is independent of soil properties. The maximum radial displacement u_{max} can be determined by analytical solutions or 2D numerical calculations for the analyzed case. Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) proposed a complete LDP solution that covered both the region ahead and behind the face. Unlu and Gercek (2003) suggested that the LDP does not follow one continuous function, but two functions, one describing the LDP ahead of the face and one behind the face.

Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) advanced the LDP relation to account for the effects of large plastic zone development assuming perfectly-plastic conditions with no dilation. This solution is valid from the elastic case to an extended plastic zone case. The Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) LDP solution also covered both the region ahead of the face and behind the face with two different equations:

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = u_0^* \cdot e^{(X^*)} \quad \text{for } X < 0 \quad (4.2)$$

$$u^*(X) = \frac{u}{u_{max}} = 1 - (1 - u_0^*) e^{-\frac{3X^*}{2R_p^*}} \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Here, R_p^* is the normalized plastic radius, $R_p^* = R_p/R_0$, R_p is the plastic radius, and u_0^* is the normalized radial displacement at the face, according to Equation 4.4.

$$u_0^* = \frac{u_0}{u_{max}} = \frac{1}{3} e^{-0.15 \left(\frac{R_p}{R_0} \right)} \quad (4.4)$$

1.11.2 Strain hardening small-strain soil model

In this study, soil behavior is described by the elastoplastic HSS model (referred to as Plastic-Hardening with small-strain stiffness model by Itasca, 2009). The shear failure in this model obeys the Mohr-Coulomb (MC) failure criterion while the plasticity is governed by two yield surfaces, the shear hardening yield surface (describing the deviatoric hardening mechanism), and the volumetric yield cap (describing the isotropic hardening mechanism). The volumetric yield cap is not discussed here as the failure mechanism around an unsupported tunnel is of a deviatoric nature, and the volumetric yield cap is neglected in this study. A total of 14 main input parameters are needed for the HSS model, as presented in Table 3.1.

Unlike in the elastic perfectly plastic Mohr-Coulomb Model, the stress-strain relationship in the HSS model is assumed to be a hyperbolic curve in primary loading (virgin compression loading). The hyperbolic relationship (Figure 3.2) that was originally described by Kondner (1963) and later adapted by Duncan and Chang (1970) can be formulated as:

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{q_a}{2E_{50}} \frac{1}{1-q/q_a} \quad q < q_f \quad (4.5)$$

where ε_1 is the axial strain in a standard triaxial compression test, E_{50} is the tangent modulus at 50% of the ultimate deviatoric stress, q_f , and q is the deviatoric stress $q = \sigma_3 - \sigma_1$ for triaxial compression. The asymptotic deviatoric stress q_a is defined by q_f and the failure ratio R_f , and is defined as

$$q_a = \frac{q_f}{R_f} \quad (4.6)$$

where R_f is the ratio between q_f and q_a , and is commonly taken as 0.9 (Schanz 1999). q_f is derived from the Mohr–Coulomb failure criterion and is defined as

$$q_f = \frac{2 \sin \varphi'}{1 - \sin \varphi'} (\sigma'_3 + c' \cot \varphi') \quad (4.7)$$

For shear stresses equal to q_f , the behavior is assumed to be perfectly plastic (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Schematic representation of the hyperbolic stress-strain relationship in triaxial compression and definition of parameters (Itasca. 2009).

Schanz (1999) extended this formulation (Eq. 4.5) to the elastoplastic framework of the standard hardening soil (HS) model, where the shear yield function is given as:

$$f^s = \frac{q_a}{E_{50}} \frac{1}{1-q/q_a} - \frac{2q}{E_{ur}} - \gamma^p \quad (4.8)$$

Here, E_{50} is the stress-dependent secant modulus (Eq. 4.10), E_{ur} is the stress-dependent un/reloading modulus (Eq. 11), and γ^p is the plastic shear strain. For the triaxial case, assuming that the plastic volumetric strains are negligible, Schanz (1999) defined

$$\gamma^p = 2\varepsilon_1^p \quad (4.9)$$

For every stress increment, there is a corresponding incremental elastic and plastic strains if the soil is undergoing primary loading, or only elastic strain if it is under unloading-reloading (Figure 3.2).

In the HS model, soil stiffness is described by two main non-linear stiffness parameters, the secant modulus (E_{50}) and the unloading/reloading modulus (E_{ur}), which are stress-dependent according to the following power law:

$$E_{50} = E_{50}^{ref} \left(\frac{c' \cos \varphi' - \sigma_3' \sin \varphi'}{c' \cos \varphi' - p^{ref} \sin \varphi'} \right)^m \quad (4.10)$$

$$E_{ur} = E_{ur}^{ref} \left(\frac{c' \cos \varphi' - \sigma_3' \sin \varphi'}{c' \cos \varphi' - p^{ref} \sin \varphi'} \right)^m \quad (4.11)$$

where E_{50}^{ref} is the reference secant modulus and E_{ur}^{ref} is the reference un/reloading modulus corresponding to the reference pressure p^{ref} . The actual stress-dependent modulus depends on the minor principal effective stress σ_3' . The degree of stress dependency is given by the power m , where a value of $m = 0$ sets a stress independent soil stiffness, and as the value of m increases, the stiffness of the soil is more stress-dependent. Typical values of m range between 0.3-1.0 and are closer to 0.5 for sands and between 0.7-1.0 for clay (Benz 2006). In general, $E_{50}^{ref} < E_{ur}^{ref}$ and the ratio $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ is between 2 to 6, and an average value of 3 usually assumed. Additional parameters needed for the HS model related to the volumetric cap (which is neglected in this study), are the reference oedometer modulus (E_{oed}^{ref}), the coefficient of earth pressure for normally consolidated conditions (K_o^{NC}), and over consolidation ratio (OCR). Note that K_o^{NC} is an input parameter needed for the HS model volumetric cap and not the lateral earth pressure ratio used in the analysis.

Two additional parameters are required for the small strain extension introduced to the standard HS model by Benz (2006) for the HSS model, the initial stiffness modulus E_0^{ref} and the reference shear strain γ_{70} . The non-linear small strain stiffness is defined by Eq. 4.12 as follows

$$G_s = \frac{G_0}{1 + 0.385 \frac{\gamma}{\gamma_{70}}} \quad (4.12)$$

where $G_0 = E_0/2(1 - \nu)$, and

$$E_0 = E_0^{ref} \left(\frac{c' \cos \varphi' - \sigma_3' \sin \varphi'}{c' \cos \varphi' - p^{ref} \sin \varphi'} \right)^m \quad (4.13)$$

The reference shear strain γ_{70} is the value at which the secant shear modulus is about 70% of G_0 , typically between 10^{-4} to $7 \cdot 10^{-4}$. E_0^{ref} can be estimated from in-situ tests and is typically 6 to 14 times E_{50}^{ref} ($6 < E_0^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref} < 14$).

Table 3.1. Description of HSS model parameters (including the volumetric cap parameters).

HSS model		
Parameter	Units	Description
ϕ'	[°]	Effective friction angle
c'	[MPa]	Effective cohesion
ψ'	[°]	Dilatancy angle
E_{50}^{ref}	[MPa]	Reference secant modulus
E_{oed}^{ref}	[MPa]	Reference oedometer modulus
E_{ur}^{ref}	[MPa]	Reference un/reloading modulus
p^{ref}	[MPa]	Reference pressure
ν_{ur}	[-]	Un/reloading Poisson's ratio
m	[-]	Power for stress-level dependency of stiffness
K_{nc}	[-]	K_o -value for normal consolidation
R_f	[-]	Failure ratio
OCR	[-]	Over consolidation ratio
E_0^{ref}	[MPa]	Small strain modulus
$\gamma_{0.7}$	[-]	Shear strain at which $G_s=0.7G_0$

1.12 Finite Difference Modeling Approach

Two modeling approaches were used for the development and verification of the HSS LDP equation, including a 3D model with vertical symmetry, and an axisymmetric model (Figures 4.3 and 4.4). The axisymmetric model configuration is utilized in this study as part of the comprehensive parametric study to reduce the computation time required for the time-consuming 3D model. For the purpose of this study, both models were performed using the commercial software package FLAC3D based on a generalized finite difference method (FDM).

Both models begin from an initial undisturbed condition subjected to isotropic stress conditions ($K_o=1$) of $\sigma'_o=1800$ kPa representing a tunnel constructed at a depth of 100 m (assuming soil dry unit weight of 18 kN/m³). The influence of the stress gradient due to gravity is ignored as typical when assuming deep tunnel conditions (as seen in Vlachopoulos and Diederichs, 2009, Prassetyo and Gutierrez, 2018 and others). A tunnel radius of 3.5 m (typical metro size tunnel) is used for this study. The unlined tunnel construction is simulated by progressively deactivating 80 excavation regions (each 1.5 m in length). An internal pressure is applied to the excavation boundary simulating the TBM support pressure applied during closed face TBM tunneling. For both modeling approaches, drained conditions are assumed throughout the analysis, and no groundwater is modeled.

1.12.1 3D Model with Vertical Symmetry

Figure 3.3 shows the 3D model with vertical symmetry developed for this study. After a study of the boundary effects and mesh discretization, the 3D model dimensions were set to 100 m wide, 150 m long, and 84 m deep. The boundary conditions were

fixed in the normal directions (rollers) at model sides and at the bottom of the model, and the overburden pressure was applied at the model top face (Figure 3.3b). At each excavation stage, a 1.5 m long region of the tunnel was deactivated, and a normal pressure was applied to the tunnel face and to the cylindrical excavation surface. The pressure applied to the excavation boundary is constant and uniformly distributed along the entire length of the excavation.

Figure 3.3. Geometry and Boundary Conditions of the FLAC3D 3D vertical symmetry Finite-difference model

1.12.2 Axisymmetric model

Assuming a deep, circular tunnel with isotropic stress conditions, an axisymmetric model is an appropriate representation as the stress state and ground response at every point around the circular tunnel is identical. The axisymmetric model configuration developed in FLAC3D and used for this study is shown in Figure 3.4. The axisymmetric model configuration simulates a slice of the tunnel domain, as shown in Figure 3b. The axisymmetric configuration is simulated by a $\pi/100$ wedge shape mesh, centered on the tunnel symmetry axis, which is set as the tunnel center axis (Figure 3.4). The model is 100 m in width (wedge length), 150 m long, and the boundary conditions are shown in Figure 3.4. As in the 3D model, at each excavation stage, a 1.5 m long region of the tunnel was deactivated, and a normal pressure is applied to the tunnel face and to the excavation surface.

Figure 3.4. Geometry and Boundary Conditions of the FLAC3D Axisymmetric Finite-difference model

1.12.3 Analysis approach

To develop the HSS LDP solution, the influence of different degrees of elastoplastic behavior (the amount of plastic shear strain that develops) and selected input parameters of the HSS model was investigated. For this study, one type of soil was considered as the reference case and is referred to as the base model (Table 3.2). These properties are based on the Berlin sand from Benz (2006) with some variations for the parametric analysis starting point.

First, an investigation into the influence of the degree of elastoplastic behavior is conducted by a variation of the internal pressure with no change in the base model properties. The internal pressures (P_i') used for this investigation is normalized by field stress ($P_i^* = P_i' / \sigma_o'$) using normalized internal pressure values of 0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.15, and 0.1. After establishing the behavior of the base soil model under different degrees of elastoplastic behavior, a parametric study of the HSS parameters is conducted. For the parametric analysis reference case, a normalized internal pressure of $P_i^* = 0.1$ is selected, as in this range of internal pressure, in-situ stresses, and soil properties, a yield zone (defined as where the stress state reaches the MC failure envelope) develops around the tunnel. Only for the parametric analysis of ϕ' is a $P_i^* = 0.15$ used to allow for excavation stability when $\phi' = 25^\circ$.

In this parametric analysis, only one parameter out of a total of six selected input parameters has been varied independently in each analysis case (Table 3.3). The five HSS input parameters identified for this analysis are the effective friction angle (ϕ'), effective cohesion (c'), power law of stress-dependent stiffness (m), reference secant modulus (E_{50}^{ref}), and effective dilatancy angle (Ψ'). For the sensitivity analysis of E_{50}^{ref} a

constant ratio is kept between $E_{ur}^{ref} / E_{50}^{ref}$ and E_0^{ref} / E_{ur}^{ref} of 3 and 4 respectively. The influence of these ratios is investigated separately in section 3.6.

A comparison between the axisymmetric model and the 3D model is shown in Figure 3.5. The axisymmetric model shows a good correlation with the 3D model and allows the use of the less time-consuming computation of the axisymmetric model for the parametric analysis.

Table 3.2. HSS base soil model parameters.

Parameter	Units	HSS base model	MC model
ϕ'	[°]	35	35
c'	[kPa]	3	3
ψ'	[°]	10	10
E	[MPa]	-	530
E_{50}^{ref}	[MPa]	70	-
E_{oed}^{ref}	[MPa]	70	-
E_{ur}^{ref}	[MPa]	210	-
p^{ref}	[kPa]	100	-
v_{ur}	[-]	0.2	0.25
m	[-]	0.7	-
K_{nc}	[-]	0.57	-
R_f	[-]	0.9	-
OCR	[-]	100	-
E_0^{ref}	[MPa]	840	-
$Y_{0.7}$	[-]	0.0002	-

Figure 3.5. Comparison between the axisymmetric model and the 3D model for the HSS base parameters with a normalized internal pressure of $P_i^*=0.1$.

Table 3.3. HSS selected input parameters for parametric analysis. Each input parameter varied independently in each analysis case

Parameter	Unit	Values for analysis
ϕ'^4	[°]	25, 27, 30, 33, 36
c'	[kPa]	0, 50, 100, 150, 200
ψ'	[°]	0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10
E_{50}^{ref}	[MPa]	35, 70, 140, 210, 280 420
m	-	0, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9

1.13 Excavation response of HSS material

This section discusses the ground response around a tunnel excavated in HSS material, and the differences with the ground response of tunnel excavation in EPP MC material. For this comparison, the strength parameters ϕ' , c' , and ψ' are the same for both the HSS model and the MC model. The elastic modulus, E , of the MC model is derived from Eq. 4.10 using E_{50}^{ref} and initial stress conditions. Figure 3.6 illustrates the differences between the HSS model and the EPP MC model stress strain curve. The initial stiffness of the HSS model is higher than the MC linear-elastic stiffness. However, as the strain increases, the HSS stiffness decreases given the elastoplastic response, resulting in a hyperbolic stress-strain curve up to the point where the MC failure criterion is reached and perfectly plastic behavior is seen. The MC material reaches failure at a significantly lower strain due to its linear elastic stiffness. Figure 3.6 also shows the

⁴ For the sensitivity analysis of ϕ' a $P_i^*=0.15$ is used

unloading reloading of both models, where the HSS un/reloading stiffness is five times higher given the higher value of E_{ur}^{ref} and E_o^{ref} compared to the MC single E value.

Figure 3.6. Stress-strain curve of HSS and MC soils in triaxial compression

Figure 3.7a shows the normalized stress distribution around an unlined tunnel in HSS and MC materials calculated by 3D FDM for the base soil properties in Table 3.2, with $P_t^* = 0.1$. A significant difference is observed between the HSS and the MC materials stress distribution, especially with regards to the tangential stress (σ'_t). For the EPP case, a distinct peak in σ'_t is located at the boundary between the elastic zone and the yield zone, marking the yield radius, R_p (also referred to as the plastic radius), which is defined as the boundary between the elastic zone and the yield zone. In the HSS material, a more gradual variation in σ'_t is observed around the tunnel opening, with the peak in σ'_t located farther from the tunnel boundary compared to the EPP case, and at a lower magnitude. The position of the peak σ'_t is used to define a new parameter, the stress redistribution radius, R_{sr} , which is the distance from the tunnel center to the peak in tangential stress (Figure 3.7a).

Figure 3.7b shows the distribution of the deviatoric stress $q = (\sigma'_3 - \sigma'_1)/2$ along the normalized radial distance. The MC maximum q is observed at the plastic radius with a very distinct peak. However, for the HSS material, the maximum q is located at a much closer distance to the tunnel center compared to the maximum σ'_t . While the maximum q for the HSS material is lower than for the MC material, it is much more distinct than the maximum HSS σ'_t . The position of the peak q is also used to define a new parameter, the deviatoric stress radius, R_q , which is the distance from the tunnel center to the peak in q (Figure 3.7b).

While for the MC material the position of the maximum q or σ'_t value marks the transition from elastic behavior to purely plastic behavior, for a tunnel excavated in HSS material, there is no fully elastic zone around the tunnel. Plastic strains (as part of the elastoplastic behavior described by Eq. 4.7) develop from the initiation of shearing

(Varakas et al. 2018). For HSS material, the values of R_q and R_{sr} are indicators of the degree of elastoplastic response of the ground. However, only R_q is discussed further, given its more distinct peak for practical implementation in the HSS LDP solution.

Figure 3.7. Normalized stress distribution vs. normalized distance from tunnel center at the tunnel spring-line elevation in an unlined tunnel excavated in HSS, and MC materials. (a) Shows the tangent stress σ'_t , and radial stress σ'_r , and (b) the deviatoric stress q along the normalized radial distance

For a tunnel excavated in HSS material, a yield zone (perfectly plastic zone, not to be confused with the elastoplastic behavior described by Eq. 4.7) may develop around the tunnel if the stress state reaches the MC envelope. This yield zone around the tunnel is smaller (or may not develop at all) compared to a tunnel excavated in MC material under the same conditions and with equivalent properties. For the analysis case shown in Figure 3.7, a yield zone does develop around the tunnel for the base HSS soil properties (Figure 3.8c), with a normalized yield radius of about 1.1. This is significantly smaller than in the MC material (Figure 3.8b) with a normalized yield radius of about 2.3. For the HSS case, the development of plastic strain prior to meeting the MC failure criterion in the elastoplastic zone outside the yield zone results in a smaller yield zone. The significance of the plastic strain as part of the elastoplastic behavior can be seen in the effective stress path (ESP) shown in Figure 3.8a. For both the HSS and the MC materials, Figure 3.8a shows the drained ESP of a point located 4 cm away from the spring-line excavation boundary (shown by point o on the top of Figure 3.8a) measured in the 3D model. Starting from point A, which shows the initial isotropic stress state, the stress path starts to move up vertically for MC material as the tunnel face advances towards the measurement point until it approaches the MC failure line at a distance of 1.5 m from the face. The HSS stress path moves in a curved line, up and to the left due to the development of plastic strain and the shear hardening law in Eq. 4.7. Once substantial shear strain develops, the stress path moves down towards the MC failure line. The stress state at the position of the face is shown by points B and B' for the HSS and the MC respectively.

Figure 3.9 shows the normalized deviatoric stress distribution (Figure 3.9a) and the plastic shear strain, γ_p (Figure 3.9b) vs. the normalized distance from the tunnel center for three P_i^* values, 0.5, 0.2 and 0.1 for the HSS material. With the increase of P_i^* , the location of the peak deviatoric stress is closer to the tunnel center (R_q is smaller) indicating an increase of plastic behavior with a decrease in P_i^* . This is also shown in Figure 3.9b where for a decrease in P_i^* the maximum γ_p (at the tunnel boundary) increases, indicating an increase of plastic behavior. This plastic strain that develops as part of the elastoplastic behavior described by Eq. 4.7 decreases as the distance from the tunnel increases. The degree of plastic deformation in this elastoplastic zone depends mostly on the in-situ stresses, soil properties, and support pressure, and a yield zone may or may not develop depending if the stress state reaches the MC failure envelope.

Figure 3.8. Effective stress paths (ESP) of a point next to the tunnel spring-line for both the HSS and the MC materials (b) yielded zones around the tunnel excavated in EPP material, (c) yielded zones around the tunnel excavated in HSS material. The measurement point is located 4 cm away from the spring-line excavation boundary at point o as shown on the top of (a).

Figure 3.9. (a) Normalized deviatoric stress q distribution, and (b) plastic shear strain vs. normalized distance from tunnel center at the tunnel spring-line level in an unlined tunnel, with three different normalized internal pressures, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.5.

The influence of the soil properties and support pressure on the degree of plastic deformation in this elastoplastic zone is illustrated in Figure 3.10. The figure shows the variation in both R_q and R_p from the parametric analysis performed using the axisymmetric model. While a decrease in P_i^* , ϕ' , or c' results in an increase of both R_{sr} and R_p and almost no change in R_q or R_p for a change in E_{50}^{ref} or Ψ' , a change in m , results in the different trend for both R_q and R_p . While R_q increases with the increase in m , R_p shows the opposite behavior and decreases with the increase in m . With a value of m close to 1, no plastic zone develops around the tunnel, and the R_q is the highest, and as m is reduced, R_p increases, and the R_{sr} decreases. This is a result of the fact that m controls the soil stiffness stress dependency (Eq. 4.10). As m is higher the soil stiffness closer to the excavation boundary is reduced more due to the tunnel deconfinement, and the stress relaxation around the tunnel is greater with the peak in deviatoric stresses located farther away.

Figure 3.10. Variation of R_q and R_p vs. the parameter studied in the parametric analysis.

Figure 3.11 shows the ground reaction curve (GRC) of the tunnel crown from a 2D model, accounting for a gradual decrease of internal pressure. Figure 3.11a shows the GRC with absolute values, where the GRC shows a similar behavior of both the HSS soil and the MC soil in the initial stage, corresponding to the linear elastic response of the MC soil. The initial response of the HSS soil is stiffer than the MC soil given the unloading nature of the ground response. As the internal pressure decreases and plastic strains increase, the HSS ground response is more plastic. The curves meet around the stage where the MC response becomes plastic at around $P_i' = 900$ kPa ($P_i^* = 0.5$). However, following this point, the HSS curve exhibits lower stiffness (e.g. higher displacement for the same P_i') compared to the MC soil due to the stress-dependent stiffness (as confining stress decreases) and resulting elastoplastic response. The final displacement (at $P_i^* = 0.1$) is 75 mm for the HSS and 57 mm for the MC soil. When put in the context of normalized GRC (P_i^* vs. u^*), Figure 3.10b shows that the HSS initial response is stiffer and the two curves meet only at $P_i^* = 0.3$ and follow almost the same slope until maximum displacement is reached. Based on the GRC in Figure 3.11a, to reach the same absolute displacement (higher than 10 mm), a higher pressure is needed for the HSS soil. For a liner installed at the same absolute displacement, this results in a higher support load for the HSS soil support. However, when put into a normalized displacement context, to reach the same u^* an identical P_i^* is needed for both the HSS and the MC soil (Figure 3.11b).

Figure 3.11. Ground reaction curve (GRC) for both the HSS case and the MC case for the base model shown in Table 3.2.

1.14 HSS longitudinal displacement profile solution

While the use of the linear-elastic and the EPP soil constitutive models can result in the overestimation of convergence prior to liner installation, no LDP solution is available in the literature for strain hardening soil behavior. Figure 3.12 shows how the use of different soil constitutive models has an influence on the longitudinal displacement behavior. The LDP of a tunnel excavated in linear-elastic soil will reach full convergence at a shorter distance x from the face of the excavation compared to a tunnel excavated in EPP material (assuming the development of a plastic zone). A tunnel in EPP soil will reach full convergence at a shorter x compared to a tunnel in HSS material with the same strength parameters. Therefore, the assumption of linear-elastic or EPP behavior can result in the overestimation of convergence prior to liner installation at the shield tail and the corresponding underestimation of lining loads. Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) recognized that the difference between the linear-elastic case and the EPP case is directly linked to the development and size of the plastic zone. For the HSS case plastic strains develop farther away from the tunnel center compared to the EPP case, resulting in the different LDP behavior seen in Figure 3.12. With typical soft ground pressure balance TBM shield lengths between 1D to 1.5D, the gray area in Figure 3.12 shows the expected distance from the face the lining is typically installed in shield tunneling. For a tunnel excavated assuming linear-elastic or EPP material, convergence can be overestimated by as much as 30% and 20% respectfully compared to the HSS material (for the base model case).

Figure 3.12. LDPs from 3D numerical calculations of three different soil behaviors are shown: linear-elastic, elastic-perfectly plastic (EPP), and “Hardening soil small strain” (HSS).

The difference between the LDP of an EPP soil and a HSS soil is also seen in Figure 3.13 for different P_i^* with different sizes of plastic zones. For the $P_i^*=0.5$ case, while no plastic zone develops ($R_p=1$) for the EPP soil, and also for the HSS soil R_p and R_q are equal to 1, a significant difference is seen between the two LDPs. Despite this, in the HSS soil very low plastic strains do develop around the tunnel, as a result of shearing of the soil due to tunnel excavation. This behavior results in that the LDP of a tunnel in EPP soil with a lower P_i^* of 0.1 will reach full convergence at a shorter x compared to a tunnel in HSS soil with $P_i^*=0.5$.

Figure 3.13. LDP for EPP and HSS soils with different P_i^* of 0.5 and 0.1.

According to Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009), the distance from the face that full convergence is reached is directly linked to the development of the plastic zone. Recognizing this, the LDP solution by Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) (Eq. 4.3) is controlled by the yield radius that can be found by closed-form solutions such as Carranza-Torres and Fairhurst (2000) and Salencon (1969). Therefore, u_{max} can be estimated without numerical analysis for a deep tunnel in isotropic stress-field, and homogeneous ground.

A LDP solution describing HSS material must account for the elastoplastic behavior prior to the development of the yield zone around the tunnel. From the investigation of the internal pressure influence on the degree of elastoplastic behavior, R_q discussed in section 3.4 is linked to the LDP shape and the distance at which full convergence is achieved. Figure 3.14 shows how lower P_i^* results in a higher value of R_q and relates to LDP shape. With lower P_i^* and higher R_q , full convergence is reached farther from the face, as seen in Figure 14b. Within the typical TBM shield length, the difference in u^* is between 15-20%, for P_i^* between 0.1 to 0.5 (for the base model conditions). For a P_i^* of 0.5, no R_q develops ($R_q=R_0$) and as P_i^* is decreased to 0.2 and 0.1, R_q increases to about 2 and 3 respectively. While R_q was found to be the primary parameter controlling the LDP shape, for a variation in m , the yield radius, R_p was also found to influence the LDP shape and is also used in the HSS LDP equation. This can be seen in Figures 4.15-4.17, where for a higher R_q , full convergence is reached at a farther distance from the face. However, Figure 3.18 shows that as m increases, R_q increases, and R_p decreases with no change in the LDP.

Figure 3.14. (a) Deviatoric stress vs. the distance from the tunnel center, for a tunnel excavated in HSS material with different internal pressures. (b) LDP of the corresponding internal pressures. As R_q increases with the decreases in P_i^* , full convergence is reached farther from the face.

A HSS LDP function was developed to predict the normalized convergence as a function of X^* . Building from the Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) formulation, and based on the observation that both R_q and R_p control the shape of the LDP, a best fit function is proposed for the region behind the face:

$$u^* = 1 - (1 - u_0^*)e^{-0.6\left(\frac{X^{*0.85}}{\sqrt{R_q^* R_p^*}}\right)} \quad \text{for } X > 0 \quad (4.14)$$

where

$$u_0^* = \frac{u_0}{u_{max}} = \frac{1}{3}e^{-0.25\left(\frac{R_q}{R_0}\right)} \quad (4.15)$$

For the region in front of the face ($X < 0$) Eq. 2 is still valid together with Eq. 4.15.

Figure 15-18 shows the ability of Eq. 4.14 (referred to from here on as the HSS LDP solution) to predict the LDP for a variation in internal support pressures and HSS parameters as described above. The values of R_q and R_p used for the calculation of the HSS LDP equation are detailed in each figure. To obtain R_q and R_p for the application of the HSS LDP solution, 2D plane strain analysis or the semi-analytical computational method developed by Vrakas et al. (2018) are required (discussed in section 3.7).

Figure 3.15 shows a good fit between the LDP predicted by Eq. 4.14, and the LDP revealed by numerical analysis. The prediction degrades slightly with an increase in P_i^* . With the same HSS parameters, for high internal pressure ($P_i^*=0.5$) the tunnel response is more elastic reaching full convergence at a closer distance from the face and is well predicted by the HSS LDP equation. For the lowest internal pressure case ($P_i^*=0.1$) the tunnel response is more plastic, reaching convergence at a farther distance from the face and is also very well predicted by the HSS LDP equation.

Figure 3.15. LDP for internal pressure sensitivity analysis. Numerical analysis results are shown by the points and the HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.14) by continues lines

Figure 3.16 shows how for a lower friction angle and lower cohesion, the HSS LDP reaches full convergence farther from the face. The HSS LDP equation shows very good ability to predict this with both the R_q and the R_p increasing for a decrease in friction angle and cohesion. The variation of Ψ' and E_{50}^{ref} result in little to no change in the LDP as can be seen from Figure 3.17. Together with the fact that R_q and R_p also do not change with the variation of Ψ' and E_{50}^{ref} (Figure 3.10), the HSS LDP equation shows a very good ability to predict the LDP. The variation of m results in little to no change in the LDP (Figure 3.18); however, as seen in Figure 3.10, as m increases, R_q increases, and R_p decreases. Despite the different trends in R_q and R_p , the HSS LDP equation shows a very good ability to predict the LDP. The ability of Eq. 4.14 to predict the LDP for a variation in m relies on the use of both R_q and R_p , in the equation.

Figure 3.16. LDP for (a) friction angle and (b) cohesion sensitivity analysis. Numerical analysis results are shown by the points and the HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.14) by continues lines

Figure 3.17. LDP for (a) dilation and (b) secant modulus sensitivity analysis. Numerical analysis results are shown by the points and the HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.14) by continuous lines.

Figure 3.18. LDP for power law of stress-dependent stiffness, m , sensitivity analysis. Numerical analysis results are shown by the points and the HSS LDP solution (Eq. 14) by continuous lines.

1.15 Correction factor for different modulus ratios

As noted in section 3.3.3, the ratio between the secant modulus (E_{50}^{ref}), un/reloading modulus (E_{ur}^{ref}), and the small strain modulus (E_0^{ref}) are kept constant throughout all sensitivity analysis presented in section 3.4 and 3.5. Two additional sets of sensitivity analyses were performed to investigate the influence of the ratios $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ and E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref} . In these analyses, the value of E_{50}^{ref} is kept constant.

Figure 3.19 shows the LDPs calculated using different secant modulus and un/reloading modulus ratios ($E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$) and the variation in R_q and R_p . It can be seen that for a ratio of 2, convergence is reached at the shortest distance from the face despite almost no change in R_p and only a slightly lower R_q compared to the base model. For a ratio of 5, convergence is reached farther away from the face, and R_q shows almost no change as well, and R_p is slightly higher. For a lower ratio, the value of E_{ur}^{ref} is lower, and the magnitude of elastic deformations is higher, resulting in a more elastic response that reaches convergence closer to the face. Given the change in the distance from the face, full convergence is reached while little to no change in R_q and R_p is seen, Eq. 4.14 does not predict the LDP accurately.

Figure 3.19. Sensitivity analysis of the ratio $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ with a constant $E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref}=4$. (a) LDP from numerical analysis results shown by points and the HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.14) by continuous lines. (b) Variation in R_q and R_p vs. $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$. Note that the base model is $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}=3$.

To account for the variation in stiffness ratios $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ and E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref} , a stiffness ratio factor (A) is added to Eq. 4.14, as follows

$$u^* = 1 - (1 - u_0^*)e^{-0.6 \cdot A \left(\frac{X^{*0.85}}{\sqrt{R_q^* R_p^*}} \right)} \quad (4.16)$$

This correction factor is defined as:

$$A = \left(\frac{1}{E^* \cdot E_{SS}^*} \right)^{0.6/E_{SS}^*} \quad (4.17)$$

where

$$E^* = \sqrt{\frac{E_{ur} - 1}{\frac{E_{50}}{2}}} \quad (4.18)$$

$$E_{ss}^* = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{E_0}{E_{ur}} + 1}{\frac{E_{ur}}{5}}} \quad (4.19)$$

Figures 4.20-4.21 show the HSS LDP solution with the correction, according to Eq. 4.16 and 4.17. Figure 3.20 shows good agreement of the corrected LDP equation with different $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ ratios and a constant E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref} ratio of 4. Figure 3.21 also shows a good agreement of the corrected LDP equation with a constant $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ ratio of 3 and a variation of E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref} , with ratios of 1, 2, 3, and 4.

Figure 3.20. Corrected HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.16) prediction for a variation in the ratio $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}$ with a constant $E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref}=4$ and a P_i^* of 0.1. LDP from numerical analysis results shown by points, and the corrected HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.16) by continuous lines. Note that the base model is $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}=3$.

Figure 3.21. Corrected HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.16) prediction for a variation in the ratio E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref} with a constant $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}=3$. LDP from numerical analysis results shown by points, and the corrected HSS LDP solution (Eq. 4.16) by continuous lines. Note that the base model is $E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}=3$ and $E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref}=4$.

1.16 Application of the HSS LDP Equation

For the implementation of the HSS LDP solution, R_q and R_p must be calculated first. This can be done by 2D plane strain analysis or by a semi-analytical computational method developed by Vrakas et al. (2018). This section demonstrates the ability of the HSS LDP solution to predict the LDP for three soil types from the literature relying on R_q and R_p values calculated from 2D plane strain analysis. Three soil types calibrated for the HSS model by Benz (2006) and Ravi et al. (2018) are used. Table 3.4 summarizes the HSS parameters of the Heinenoord clay, Torino soil, and Berlin sand. For this analysis, isotropic stress conditions are assumed, with lower in-situ stress of 900 kPa, representing a tunnel constructed at a depth of 50 m (assuming soil dry unit weight of 18 kN/m³) and the P_i^* value used here was 0.3. A tunnel radius of 3.5 m is used also for this analysis. Figure 3.22 shows a very good ability of the HSS LDP solution using R_q and R_p values from 2D plane strain analysis to predict the axisymmetric LDP.

Table 3.4. HSS base soil model parameters.

Parameter	Units	Heinenoord clay	Torino soil	Berlin sand-L3
ϕ'	[°]	31	36	38
c'	[kPa]	7	72	0
ψ'	[°]	0	0	6
E_{50}^{ref}	[MPa]	24	75	105
E_{ur}^{ref}	[MPa]	70	225	315
p^{ref}	[kPa]	100	100	100
ν_{ur}	[-]	0.2	0.2	0.2
m	[-]	0.9	0.7	0.55
R_f	[-]	0.9	0.9	0.9
E_0^{ref}	[MPa]	420	900	700
$\gamma_{0.7}$	[-]	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002

Figure 3.22. LDP for three soil types described in Table 4, axisymmetric numerical analysis results are shown by the points, and the corrected HSS LDP solution (Eq. 16) using R_q and R_p values from 2D plane strain analysis.

1.17 Conclusions

This paper investigates the longitudinal displacement behavior and proposes an LDP solution for soft ground tunneling characterized by the HSS model and constructed using pressure balance TBMs (slurry or EPB). The calculation of LDPs assuming linear-elastic or the EPP soil behavior compared to the more realistic HSS model can result in overestimation of the pre-convergence that will occur prior to liner installation (as seen in Figure 3.12). The GRC of the HSS and MC soils were shown to be quite similar when put into a normalized displacement context. The ability of the HSS model to simulate soil behavior more accurately than linear-elastic and EPP soil models such as the Mohr-Coulomb model (MC) is particularly important for the simulation of pressure balance shield tunneling, where the use of a non-linear constitutive model has significant

importance as the near field zone is subjected mostly to an unloading stress path with the change in confinement. This over-estimation of the pre-convergence by EPP MC was shown to be as much as 20%. Together with GRCs that shows no significant difference between the HSS and MC (when put in terms of normalized values), can result in underestimation of support loads.

Using a series of 3D and axisymmetric numerical analysis, a HSS LDP equation is developed based on Vlachopoulos and Diederichs (2009) LDP solution, while introducing a new parameter, the deviatoric stress radius (R_q). From the investigation of the internal pressure influence on the degree of elastoplastic behavior, it was found that this new parameter is linked to the rate of convergence. With a greater value of R_q , the radial displacements reach convergence farther away from the face.

A comprehensive parametric analysis was conducted for the development and validation of the HSS LDP equation (Eq. 4.14). The parametric analysis included a variation of internal support pressures (allowing different degrees of elastoplastic behavior), and a variation of selected input parameters of the HSS model. The results showed a very good ability of the HSS LDP solution to predict the tunnel LDP in HSS material. While the HSS LDP equation was developed for constant stiffness ratios ($E_{ur}^{ref}/E_{50}^{ref}=3$, and $E_0^{ref}/E_{ur}^{ref}=4$), an addition of a correction factor is needed (Eq. 4.16, and 4.17) to account for a variation in the stiffness ratios. The practical application of the HSS LDP solutions requires R_q and R_p by means of 2D plane strain analysis or by a semi-analytical computational method (Vrakas et al. 2019). The ability of the HSS LDP equation to predict the LDP of an axisymmetric model using from 2D plane strain analysis was demonstrated for three soil types from the literature. The HSS LDP solution allows better accuracy in the prediction of the longitudinal displacement profile in soft ground critical for a reliable prediction of the lining forces, surface deformation, and excavation stability.

4.1.

GROUND-STRUCTURE INTERACTION OF CROSS-PASSAGE TUNNELS CONNECTING SEGMENTALLY LINED TUNNELS

A paper to be submitted to a journal paper with Dr. Michael A. Mooney, and Dr. Marte Gutierrez as co-authors.

Abstract

Cross-passage construction incorporates complex 3D ground-structure interaction behavior as well as different load distribution mechanisms between individual segments, adjacent rings, and other temporary support elements. In this paper, an advanced 3D ground-structure interaction cross-passage numerical model is proposed and validated with rare field data from the Seattle Northgate Link tunnel project, including data from strain gauges installed in segmental lining rings and convergence monitoring. This 3D ground-structure interaction model presented in detail for the first time in available literature is used to achieve a better understanding of the load development in support systems of cross-passages, mainly at the openings created in the segmental lining of the running tunnels. The presented model details complex ground-structure interaction aspects that should be taken into account for both shield tunneling (running tunnels) and cross-passage excavation. The results show the difference between the loading process at the break-in and at the break-out. The most critical points in regard to the load capacity of the cross-passage opening support elements are found to be the segmental lining above and below the openings, and the bicone dowels shear capacity.

1.18 Introduction

Cross-passages are an essential requirement for emergency egress in modern twin transit tunnel systems. Single-pass pre-cast concrete segmental lining systems are widely used in transit tunnel projects in sensitive urban environments. In these single-pass segmental lining systems, the lining serves as the initial and final support system and must remain watertight and within serviceability condition. The construction of cross-passages requires the formation of openings in the running tunnels, where one or more rings are usually cut (Figure 4.1). The compression hoop-force action is interrupted (Figure 4.1) as a result of the opening in the segmental lining, and the stability of the ring is compromised (Lee and Choi, 2017). These hoop forces must be transferred to other structural components installed either before cutting open the lining or during the segmental ring erection. Some commonly found temporary support structures for cross-passage openings are full ring beam, vertical steel propping with or without a header beam, and steel segments (Lee and Choi, 2017, Frodl 2019). In recent years, coupling elements such as steel dowels and shear bicone dowels, are increasingly utilized (Lee and Choi, 2017, Walter et al. 2019, Ring 2019). The use of these coupling elements can reduce the construction complexities and costs. However, with the more common opening support structures having a higher load capacity, the use of coupling elements is less conservative, increasing the risk of failure in case of unexpected higher loads.

Cross-passage construction incorporates complex 3D ground-structure interaction behavior as well as different load distribution mechanisms between individual segments, adjacent rings, and other temporary support elements. Several modeling configurations are typically used for cross-passage construction calculations, from simple 2D strut-and-tie models, through 3D shell-spring models, to complex ground-structure interaction models (Walter et al. 2019). As a result of the cross-passage opening and excavation, stress redistribution can occur in the ground surrounding the cross-passage (Walter et al. 2019), and tunnel confinement stresses change as the cross-passage is excavated. Bedded shell models are not able to model the ground behavior accurately (Ring 2016), and 3D ground-structure interaction modeling is required to capture all the aspects for evaluating the structural forces for design.

Despite the complexity of cross-passage construction, and the complex 3D ground-structure interaction behavior, little research is available in the literature on cross-passage openings in segmentally lined tunnels. Most of the work available covers case studies and construction method overviews. In this paper, an advanced 3D ground-structure interaction numerical model is used to achieve a better understanding of the load development in support systems of cross-passages, mainly at the openings created in the segmental lining of the running tunnels. With little available literature on the influence of the assumptions used in 3D numerical modeling, this paper is the first to propose and validate a 3D cross-passage numerical model using rare segmental lining load data. The presented model details complex ground-structure interaction aspects that should be taken into account for both shield tunneling (running tunnels) and cross-passage excavation. For the running tunnels, this includes the jointed segmental lining, relaxation due to pre-convergence, grout annulus, and the non-linear soil behavior using the hardening soil constitutive model. For the cross-passage excavation, this includes the removal of segmental lining at the opening, temporary support elements, segmental lining coupling effects, step by step top-heading and bench excavation, initial shotcrete layer, full shotcrete thickness at a lag of one stage, and shotcrete time-dependent hardening.

Figure 4.1. Axial (thrust) stress distribution around an opening in segmental tunnel lining (Lee and Choi, 2017).

1.19 Field Measurement

1.19.1 Northgate Link Project

The Northgate Link Extension project includes 5.6 km of twin bored tunnels and 23 cross passages. The tunnels run north from the University of Washington to Maple Leaf Portal in north Seattle (Epel et al. 2018). The twin bored tunnels were constructed using two EPBM with an excavation diameter of 6.64 m and a shield diameter of 6.44 m. The two tunnels were constructed with a center to center distance of about two diameters. The tunnels were supported with a 25 cm thick single pass, gasketed conventionally steel-reinforced segmental lining, with an extrados diameter of 6.25 m. Each ring is comprised of four full-size segments and key and counter key segments with a nominal width of 1.5 m, and a universal ring concept having an overall ring taper of 69.9 mm.

With rare segmental strain gauge data and convergence monitoring data collected during the construction of cross-passage 39, this paper discusses and analyzes the construction process of cross-passage 39. This cross-passage was excavated through cohesionless sands and gravels (CSG) with till and till-like deposits (TLD) at the surface (as can be seen in Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Northgate Link geological conditions of the cross-passage 39.

The cross-passage was conventionally mined with an excavation width of 5 m and an excavation height of 5.5 m. The support system included 20 cm of shotcrete (including 5 cm of flashcrete), 3 bar lattice girders spaced at 90 cm, and systematic 3 m long spilling. The excavation of the cross-passage was performed from the first tunnel

(NB) towards the second (SB) tunnel, where the instrumented rings were located. The excavation was performed by top heading and bench with round lengths of about 1 m.

The segmental lining of the main tunnel was saw-cut, creating a 3x3 m² opening (the width equaling exactly two segments). The opening was supported by 6 shear bicone dowels that were pre-installed on each segment's circumferential joint and 4 shear bicone dowels on each key or counter key circumferential joint (32 in total per each circumferential joint). The Anixter 375M shear bicone dowels have an ultimate shear capacity of 375 kN. Each bicone dowel is 243 mm long with an outer polyamide casing and a steel core diameter of 35 mm. Three circumferential joints were connected at each opening by the shear bicone dowels, namely, the two rings that were cut and the adjacent ring on each side (see Figure 4.3). The shear bicone dowels were used to transfer the load from the opened segmental rings to the adjacent rings. During the design process of the Northgate Link project, shear tests were conducted on bicone dowels embedded in reinforced concrete segments. The ultimate shear force capacity and allowable shear force capacity determined from these tests were 190 kN and 135 kN, respectively. However, the design bicone dowel maximum shear force expected at the cross-passage opening was about 400 kN when no additional support measures are used. To overcome the shear bicone dowels capacity limitation, vertical steel propping was installed at the break-out and break-in of the cross-passage discussed in this paper, reducing the design bicone dowel maximum shear force to 70 kN.

Figure 4.3. (a) Cross-passage opening support measures used at cross-passage 39, with 32 bicone dowels and vertical steel props. (b) Shear bicone dowel illustration.

1.19.2 Instrumentation and Monitoring

As part of the monitoring program, foil strain gauges with full Wheatstone bridge and connected by wireless RFID transmission, were installed in select pre-cast concrete segments (Soundtransit, 2013c). Within each selected ring, three segments were instrumented – two full-size segments plus a key or counter key. Each instrumented segment was outfitted with a set of two foil strain gauges welded to the reinforcement cage, one at the intrados, and one at the extrados. The orientation of the strain gauges allowed measurement of the circumferential strain and interpretation of the stress developed in the pre-cast segments. With known geometry and strain gauge depth, the

measurements collected from a set of two strain gauges allowed for the estimation of both thrust force (hoop force) and bending moment. The sign conventions used convey positive values for compressive thrust force and bending moment when the segment intrados is in tension. In the discussed cross-section, only two rings were instrumented at the Break-in (SB) tunnel. One instrumented ring was saw-cut for the cross-passage entrance (will be referred to as opening ring), and the second instrumented ring is adjacent to the opening (will be referred to as adjacent ring) (see Figure 4.4). Unfortunately, neither the vertical steel props nor the bicone dowels installed at the cross-passage openings were monitored, despite their important role in load redistribution.

Figure 4.4. Plan view of cross-passage-39 with the different monitoring systems locations. The strain gauge instrumented rings are marked in green, and the convergence monitoring cross-sections are marked in red.

Convergence monitoring was performed in both running tunnels at the cross-passage openings and inside the cross passages. Three cross-sections in each running tunnel at each cross-passage opening were instrumented (see Figure 4.4). In each cross-section, five optical reflective targets were installed according to the configuration shown in Figure 4.5. A manual survey was performed on a daily basis, beginning 20 days prior to break-out. Inside each cross-passage, two cross-sections were instrumented in the first one-third of the excavation length and the second one-third of the excavation length. Three targets were installed in each cross-section, one at the crown and two at the spring-line of the cross-passage, as shown in Figure 4.5. The targets were installed in the full initial lining (20 cm of shotcrete) of the top heading approximately 1 m from the face of excavation. The first measurement (“zero” measured convergence) was taken before advancing to the next round of excavation. With maximum displacement measurements of up to 5 mm only and measurement accuracy of ± 1 mm, a connection between specific activities and the convergence monitoring could not be determined. Further, to establish a trend of behavior, the convergence monitoring data was analyzed using a moving average filter.

Figure 4.5. Convergence monitoring optical target locations. On the left are running tunnel target locations and on the right cross-passage target location.

1.20 Numerical Model Description

The 3D numerical model was developed using the commercial software package FLAC3D (Itasca 2009), based on a generalized finite difference method (FDM). The complex mesh was generated by SALOME Mesh (Ribes and Caremoli, 2007). The 3D model dimensions were set to 100 m wide, 75 m long, and 60 m high (Figure 4.6). The advanced 3D numerical model presented here captures the important components in both shield tunneling and cross-passage excavation. For the running tunnels, this includes the jointed segmental lining (Figure 4.6b), relaxation due to pre-convergence, grout annulus, and the non-linear soil behavior using the hardening soil small-strain constitutive model. For the cross-passage excavation, this includes the removal of segmental lining at the opening, temporary support elements (shear bicone dowels and vertical steel props), segmental lining coupling effects, step by step top-heading and bench excavation, initial shotcrete (flashcrete) layer (only 5 cm thick), full shotcrete thickness at a lag of one stage, and shotcrete time-dependent hardening.

Figure 4.6. FLAC3D model general configuration

1.20.1 Running Tunnels Construction Process

The excavation of the running tunnels creates a disturbance in the surrounding ground. Depending on the in-situ stress conditions, the soil strength, and the excavation process, plastic strains will develop around each running tunnel. These plastic strains can influence the behavior of the ground during cross-passage construction. For an accurate simulation of closed face TBM tunneling, step by step 3D numerical modeling is commonly used (Epel et al. 2020, Ninic and Meschke 2017, Do et al. 2013b). However, given the high complexity of cross-passage construction modeling, the excavation of the running tunnels requires simplifications to reduce calculation time with minimal influence on the accuracy of the results. In this paper, the convergence confinement method (CCM) is used in order to simplify the simulation of the running tunnel construction process while accounting for the 3D construction effects (e.g., the main tunnel advance is not modeled directly). In the CCM, the ground is allowed to converge prior to lining installation. The degree of pre-convergence depends mostly on the TBM internal pressure, and the distance from the face the lining is installed (Epel et al. 2020).

For the simulation of pre-convergence, the CCM was implemented by an incremental reduction of the internal confinement pressure. The transition from initial geostatic stresses to grout-pressure/machine-pressure state is expressed by Eq. 5.1 (Moller 2006):

$$\sigma' = (1 - \lambda)\sigma'_o + \lambda \cdot \sigma'_g \quad (5.1)$$

where σ'_g is the effective grout pressure ($\sigma'_g = \sigma_g - \text{pore water pressure}$), λ is the relaxation factor calculated by CCM equations, and σ'_o is the initial normal stress (Eq. 5.2). The initial normal stress is the undisturbed geostatic stress normal to the excavation boundary and can be found for any point along the tunnel perimeter by the function of the initial undisturbed geostatic vertical effective stress, σ'_{vo} and horizontal effective stress, σ'_{ho} as seen in Eq. 5.2 (Moller 2006):

$$\sigma'_o = \sigma'_{ho} \sin^2 \alpha + \sigma'_{vo} \cos^2 \alpha \quad (5.2)$$

The CCM procedure is implemented for each running tunnel accounting for a shield annulus pressure of 80 kPa with a relaxation factor of $\lambda=0.8$ prior to lining installation.

1.20.2 Soil Constitutive Model

In this study, the hardening soil small-strain (HSS) model (referred to by Itasca 2009 as the plastic-hardening small strains) is used. Based on the work of Schanz (1999) and Benz (2006), the HSS model is characterized by a frictional Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, stress-dependent soil stiffness, and different unloading/reloading stiffness compared to the virgin loading. For the simulation of mechanized tunneling, the use of a non-linear constitutive model such as the HSS model has significant importance as the near field zone is subjected initially to an unloading stress path, due

to changing confinement conditions from tunnel excavation (Arash et al. 2018, Do et al. 2013c).

The HSS model parameters were determined from the results of available triaxial tests and pressuremeter tests detailed in Epel et al. (2020), and are presented in Table 4.1. With the tunnel excavated through the highly permeable CSG material, all calculations have been performed under drained conditions and assuming a lateral earth pressure coefficient, $K_o=0.6$.

Table 4.1. Input parameters of the HSS constitutive model.

Description	Symbol	Unit	CSG
Internal friction angle	ϕ'	°	41
Dilation angle	ψ'	°	9
Cohesion	c'	kPa	0
Secant stiffness in triaxial test	E_{50}^{ref}	MPa	55
Tangent stiffness in oedometer test	E_{oed}^{ref}	MPa	55
Unloading-reloading stiffness	E_{ur}^{ref}	MPa	140
Small-strain stiffness	E_0^{ref}	MPa	240
Poisson's ratio	ν	-	0.2
Exponent power	m	-	0.68
Reference stress	p^{ref}	kPa	100
Failure ratio	R_f	-	0.85

1.20.3 Modeling the Segmental Lining

The modeling of the segmental lining longitudinal and circumferential joints is critical for the accurate simulation of the opening in the segmental lining. Each segmental lining ring is composed of discrete pre-cast concrete segments assembled to form a closed ring. Tensile forces cannot be transferred between segments, and the normal force at the joint (either longitudinal or circumferential) has significant importance on the joint behavior. With a high normal force (longitudinal force at the circumferential joint and hoop force at the longitudinal joints) and low moments at the joint, the joint remains closed with only compression pressure on the entire cross-section. However, with a high bending moment, a gap will form when the pressure at the extrados/intrados becomes zero, leading to significant additional radial joint rotation. In terms of shear force transfer between segments within a ring, and more importantly, load transfer between adjacent rings, the shear coupling mechanism is characterized by a frictional mechanism. The shear stress-displacement relation at the joint depends on the normal force at the joint and the joint contact material, namely if packers are used and what material is used for the packers (Cavalaro and Aguado 2012). Without packers (concrete to concrete contact), high frictional behavior is expected together with high shear stiffness. The use of packers results in lower frictional resistance and lower shear stiffness. This behavior also varies depending on the packer material; rubber

packers show higher frictional resistance and are stiffer compared to bituminous packer (Cavalaro and Aguado 2012).

As detailed in Epel et al. (2020), the segmental lining is modeled by linear-elastic embedded liner elements (Itasca 2009). This embedded liner element is a shell element with two links at each node, permitting the interaction between the host medium (ground) and the structural element at both sides of the element. One side of the embedded liner element is connected to the surrounding ground, and the other end is manipulated to connect the adjacent segment (Figure 4.7). Modeling the connection between individual segments is done by a link connecting the nodes of each segment at the joint location. For the 3D case, each link includes six degrees of freedom, and each degree of freedom can be assigned one of three boundary conditions: free, rigid, and deformable. These boundary conditions are represented by six springs, with three translational components, K_R in the radial direction, K_A (in Figure 4.7b), and K_t tangent to the lining ring, and three rotational components (K_θ in Figure 4.7b).

The behavior of a single segmental ring is controlled by the coupling of segments at the longitudinal joints. The normal force at the longitudinal joint controlling the flexural behavior develops from the hoop forces. These forces are a function of several factors, including geostatic stresses, ground pre-convergence, soil stiffness, and more. As long as the circular segmentally lined tunnel ring remains closed, the radial and tangential translational components of the joint stiffness have a negligible effect on segmental lining behavior (Do et al. 2013a). As in Epel et al. (2020), a deformable rotational stiffness is prescribed around the axis of the longitudinal joint ($K_{\theta_{xx}}$) by a bi-linear relation as used by Thienert and Pulsfort (2011), Do et al. (2013a, b) and others. The two remaining rotational components ($K_{\theta_{zz}}$ and $K_{\theta_{yy}}$) are assumed to be rigid (Do et al. 2013a, b). The attachment conditions of the normal translational component $K_{A_{xx}}$ is by a deformable spring in compression that fails in tension. For the radial and tangential translational components ($K_{t_{yy}}$ and $K_{R_{zz}}$), a deformable spring with cut-off shear stress is used. The formation of the cross-passage opening, braking the compression hoop-force action results in a change in the initial normal forces at the longitudinal joints. If the segments are allowed to move, a release of normal force at the joint occurs, the rotational and shear coupling behavior between segments changes, and the stability of the ring can be compromised. To account for the formation of the cross-passage opening and the change in the joint normal force, the rotational and translational stiffness values are updated based on the new normal force.

Figure 4.7. Segmental lining modeling concept and node connectivity concept (after Do et al. 2013a). On the top three stiffness components are shown, the axial (K_A), radial (K_R), and rotational (K_θ) (Do et al. 2013a).

The behavior of the segmental lining system with the collaboration of adjacent rings and not as individual rings (Figure 4.8) depends on the normal force N , at the circumferential joints, and the maximum frictional resistance τ , of the joint. The longitudinal force acting normal to the circumferential joints is introduced by the TBM hydraulic jacks pushing the TBM forward. During the shield TBM tunneling process, the TBM is constantly applying a longitudinal thrust force, even during standstill, in order to compensate for the excavation face pressure. While this longitudinal jacking force is applied to the tunnel lining only for a short period during construction, some longitudinal forces remain on the lining for its service life. Arnau et al. (2012) proposed an analytical formulation to predict the remaining longitudinal force of the lining as a function of time that considers the effect of creep of the concrete and packers. Based on this solution by Arnau et al., for a time period of between 6-12 months, about 70% of the longitudinal jacking force remains in the lining (cross-passage construction started 7 months after the second tunnel was monitored rings were installed). The longitudinal jacking force varies from the maximum value during excavation (needed to advance the TBM) and to a minimal force during standstill required to compensate for the excavation face pressure. Taking into account the maximum jacking force for the coupling of adjacent rings can result in the overestimation of the joint rotational and translational stiffness and maximum joint shear stress. This is critical for the load distribution around the cross-passage opening, and the minimal jacking force should be taken based on the force needed to compensate for the excavation face pressure. Based on an average face pressure of 90 kPa, the normal stress at the circumferential joint used for joint link properties is 0.8 MPa. For a bituminous packer (used in the Northgate project) under the lowest normal force tested of 1.5 MPa, Cavalaro and Aguado (2012) found the

friction coefficient to be 0.44 and the shear stiffness to be 17 kN/mm at 80% of the max shear stress. The stiffness and the cut-off shear force value of each spring in the model is related to the area associated with each node.

Figure 4.8. Segmental lining system load sharing mechanism. The maximum joint shear resistance τ , at the circumferential joint is of a frictional mechanism controlled by the joint normal force N .

1.20.4 Shear bicone dowels and vertical steel props modeling

The magnitude of the shear force transferred by the shear coupling elements is highly dependent on the stiffness of the shear coupling element. Comparing the shear force taken by different shear coupling elements, Benno (2016) shows how with for a higher modeled linear-elastic stiffness, a higher shear force develops in the coupling elements. However, the stiffness of shear bicone dowels is non-linear, as seen in Figure 4.9, showing the shear force vs. displacement relation measured in the bicone dowels shear tests (described in section 4.2.1). Similar to Benno (2019), in the proposed 3D model, each shear bicone dowel is modeled by a tangential and radial non-linear-stiffness. The non-linear modeled bicone dowels stiffness is determined from the shear force vs. displacement relation in Figure 4.9, where only after exceeding a shear force of 20 kN any measurable shear displacement (Δu in Figure 4.8) was measured. In addition to the bicone dowels at each cross-passage opening, two vertical steel props (hollow box section 20x20 cm outside dimension with a 16 mm wall) were modeled using beam elements. The beam elements were connected to a 4 mm steel anchor plates (modeled by elastic shell elements) attached to the segments.

Figure 4.9. Shear force vs. displacement of the bicone dowel embedded in reinforced concrete shear test and the modeled non-linear- stiffness (developed based on data from Soundtransit, 2013d).

1.20.5 Cross-Passage Construction Process

The simulation of the cross-passage construction is conducted by a step by step excavation and support sequence according to the reported construction sequence of cross-passage 39 (Soundtransit, 2013b). The different activities simulated in the model include: removal of segmental lining at the opening, temporary support elements (vertical steel props installed before opening formation and shear dowels installed during segmental lining installation), segmental lining coupling effects, step by step top-heading and bench excavation, initial shotcrete (flashcrete) layer (only 5 cm thick), full shotcrete thickness at a lag of one stage, and shotcrete time-dependent hardening.

The step by step procedure was implemented with the following sequence:

- Initial geostatic conditions with a lateral earth pressure ratio of $K_0=0.6$ are applied.
- Excavation of running tunnels (section 4.3.2)
- Activation of the vertical steel props in both tunnels.
- Removal of a $3 \times 3 \text{ m}^2$ opening (the width equaling exactly two segments) at the NB (first) tunnel.
- Removal of each excavation stage according to the sequence shown in Figure 10, and application of a 5 cm shotcrete (flashcrete) layer on the excavation boundary of the last round excavated (including the face and invert).
- Increase of the shotcrete thickness of the previous round to 20 cm. Increase of the shotcrete stiffness according to a time-dependent relation by Meschke et al. (1996).
- Removal of a $3 \times 3 \text{ m}^2$ opening (width equaling exactly two segments) at the SB (second) tunnel.

Figure 4.10. Excavation sequence of cross-passage 39.

With the real excavation sequence reported in Soundtransit (2013b), the time steps between each excavation round are used to calculate the shotcrete stiffness at the corresponding stage. The time-dependent stiffness is calculated according to the relation introduced by Meschke et al. (1996) for a 28-day elastic modulus of 28 GPa. The shotcrete time-dependent stiffness was modeled by increasing the modulus of the shotcrete applied at each excavation round independently.

1.21 Results

In this section, the 3D modeling results are discussed together with thrust-moment field measurements and convergence monitoring data. Modeling results and field measurements are presented against a timeline of the construction sequence shown in Figures 5.10. The typical excavation round of the top heading (TH) took between 1-2 days (with the exception of TH-2 that took 5 days), and the typical excavation of the bench (B) took one day, excluding weekends and Christmas that took place after the excavation of TH-5.

The sequential cross-passage construction process can be divided into three main areas of interest: the break-out opening, the cross-passage tunnel, and the break-in opening. While the differentiation between the cross-passage tunnel and break-in/out is straightforward, the differentiation between break-in and break-out is important given the different loading mechanisms, as will be discussed in this section.

Displacement measurements are very small (due to manual survey as mentioned in section 1.3) and have an accuracy of +/- 1 mm. Therefore, much of the day to day 0.5 mm fluctuations in these displacements are likely not reliable and analyzed using a moving average filter. It is also worth noting that strain gauge data was recorded continuously, so their changing response is temporally accurate. Convergence monitoring data, however, was recorded manually and is reported to the nearest day

and analyzed using a moving average filter. Therefore, the temporal comparison of strain and convergence events is challenging.

1.21.1 Loading process at the break-out tunnel

Shear bicone dowels are installed during ring build at three circumferential joints at each opening. Figure 4.11 shows the predicted shear loads that develop in the bicone dowels (bicone shear forces were not measured in the field) connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring, and for the bicones connecting the two opening rings, around the break-out opening. After ring installation and before any cross-passage activities begin, no load is taken by the bicones dowels, as the segmental lining system deforms uniformly (i.e., no differential displacement between rings). Once the cross-passage break-out opening is formed (day 0), a sharp increase in the tangential shear force is observed (Figure 4.11a) for the bicone dowels connecting the opening rings to the adjacent rings, while very low tangential shear forces develop at the bicone dowels connecting the two opening rings. Figure 4.11(b) shows that radial bicone dowel shear forces are very low after the cross-passage break-out is opened. Low radial forces develop as the lining is still confined by the surrounding soil, while only tangential bicone dowel forces develop as the hoop forces are transferred to the adjacent rings, as both opening rings are cut, and thrust hoop action is broken. Part of the forces are redistributed to the closed adjacent rings by bicone dowels, and some taken by vertical steel props that see an increase in thrust force of about 670 kN (Figure 4.11c). After the first TH round is excavated, an increase in bicone dowel tangential shear forces and a slight decrease in steel props thrust force occurs. The tangential force of the bicone dowels connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring increases by 20-60% and the vertical steel props thrust force decreases by about 15%. The bicone dowel radial shear force also increases after the excavation of TH-1 at the bicone dowels connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring. Positive radial shear forces indicate the opening ring is deflecting outwards relative to the adjacent ring, and negative radial shear forces indicate the opposite relative deflection. The positive radial shear force of the bicone dowels closest to the opening (marked in red and green in Figure 4.11b) show the cut segments are deflecting outwards and the next set of bicone dowels located closer to the crown (marked in blue in Figure 4.11) deflect inwards indicating the opening ring is squatting relative to the adjacent ring. Both radial and tangential shear bicone dowel forces do not change much as the cross-passage excavation advances, except for the radial shear force of the bicone dowels under the opening (marked in green) as a result of the first bench excavation. Unlike the bicone dowel tangential shear force, the vertical steel prop force is influenced by the first excavation stages with an increase of about 20% after the excavation of TH-2 and a decrease of about 30% after the excavation of B-1 (Figure 4.11c).

Figure 4.11. Temporary support elements force predicted by 3D modeling at the NB tunnel (break-out opening) vs. time in days from break-out. Bicone dowels (a) tangential shear forces and (b) radial shear forces. The color legend correlates to the bicone dowel color position in the top right of the figure. Filled markers show the bicone dowels connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring, and the unfilled markers show the bicone dowels connecting the two opening rings. (c) Predicted steel prop thrust force.

The hoop force transfer from the opening ring to the adjacent ring can also be observed in the predicted lining load diagram in Figure 4.12 (strain gauges were installed only at the break-in (SB) tunnel), where selected stages are presented on each diagram. As the cross-passage opening is formed, the thrust force (at the mid-width of the modeled rings) in the opening ring (Figure 12d) decreases by about 50% just above the opening and only about 5% at the opposite side from the opening. As seen in Figure 4.11, some thrust force is transferred by the bicone dowels to the adjacent ring resulting in an increase of about 20% in thrust force of the adjacent ring (Figure 4.12b) after the cross-passage opening is formed. This is followed by another increase after the excavation of TH-1 with a maximum thrust force 60% above the original thrust force. This change in thrust force at the adjacent ring is mostly at the side closer to the opening as the opposite side the thrust force varies by no more than 10%.

Figure 4.12c shows how the bending moment diagram of the opening ring did not change much due to the formation of the cross-passage opening, as the segments were cut very close to the point where bending moments change from positive to negative. A very high bending moment develops above the opening after the first top heading excavation, and below the opening after the first bench excavation, as the soil confining the cut ring is excavated up to the point where the maximum bending moment is

observed. The removal of the soil confinement allows the segments to deform at one side while the remaining part of the segment is still confined and restrained, resulting in a high bending moment. For the closed adjacent ring, a similar confinement condition results in a high negative bending moment at the spring-line next to the opening and a high positive bending moment above the cross-passage crown and below the cross-passage invert.

Figure 4.12. Segmental lining loads at the (a) & (b) adjacent ring and (c) & (d) the opening ring of the break-out (NB) tunnel. (a) & (c) show bending moments (kN-m/m) and (b) & (d) show thrust force (kN/m) diagrams at the mid-width of the modeled rings. The position of the cross-passage opening is shown by the shaded area.

At the NB tunnel, available monitoring data included only daily manual convergence monitoring. Figure 4.13 shows the field convergence monitoring and the 3D modeled lining deformation at the same locations vs. days after break-out. One day prior to break-out, displacements are initialized (zero reading). Both the adjacent ring (Figure 4.13a) and the opening ring (Figure 4.13b) show an overall squatting behavior as the cross-passage tunnel is excavated, as monitoring points M1 and M2 move downwards and point M5 moves upwards. Horizontal displacements are not shown, as measured values are smaller than the survey tolerance.

Figure 4.13. NB tunnel (break-out location) field convergence monitoring and the 3D model lining deformation at the (a) adjacent ring and (b) opening ring vs. time in days after break-out. The color legend correlates to the monitoring point color position shown on the right. Field convergence monitoring is shown by lines and markers without fill, and the 3D model lining deformation results are shown by full markers.

1.21.2 Loading Process at Cross-Passage

Two cross-sections were monitored inside the cross-passage, at TH-2, and TH-5. Figure 4.14 shows the field convergence measurements and modeled cross-passage lining displacements (at the same locations) for the two monitored cross-section. The first field measurement (zero reading of convergence) at TH-2 was taken after the excavation of TH-3, followed by a daily survey. The modeled displacements shown in

Figure 4.14a begin from the end of the excavation of TH-2 (zero reading is before excavation). The first field measurement (zero reading) is corrected to the modeled displacement after the excavation of TH-3 (which correlates to the stage the first field measurement was taken). Figure 4.14a shows that the model is able to reproduce the horizontal displacements of both the spring-line field measurements with very good agreement. The crown measurements are not shown here given that the first measurement is only reported after the excavation advanced, and no additional convergence occurred. For TH-5, the modeled displacements shown in Figure 4.14b begin from the end of the excavation of TH-5 (zero reading is before excavation). The first field measurement (zero reading) is corrected to the modeled displacement after the excavation of B-4 (which correlates to the stage the first field measurement was taken). As in TH-2, the model is able to predict the TH-5 horizontal spring-line displacements with very good agreement.

Figure 4.14. Cross-passage field convergence monitoring and the 3D model lining deformation vs. time in days from break-out. The location of each monitoring cross-section is shown on the right top side. The color legend correlates to the monitoring point color position on the right bottom. Field convergence monitoring is shown by lines and markers without fill and the 3D model lining deformation results are shown by full markers

1.21.3 Loading Process at the Break-In Tunnel

At the SB tunnel, available monitoring data included both convergence monitoring and strain gauges installed in the segmental lining. Strain gauges were installed in one opening ring and one adjacent ring. However, sufficient continuous data

is available only from one segment in the adjacent ring during cross-passage excavation. Figure 4.15 shows measured bending moments and thrust forces compared to the modeled results of the adjacent ring. The field measured thrust force begins to increase after the excavation of TH-3 on day 9, while the modeling results show an increase in thrust after the excavation of TH-2 on day 8. The measured bending moment begins to change after the excavation of B-1, with a decrease also predicted by the 3D model. The increase in thrust force trend continues until TH-5 is excavated on day 15. The 3D model results show a similar trend, with only a lower magnitude of thrust force increase. The measured bending moment shows another decrease in bending moment after the excavation of B-2, indicating the SB tunnel is squatting, deforming towards the cross-passage excavation. This squatting behavior, revealed by the decrease in bending moment (the outer fiber is in tension and inner fiber in compression), is in line with the convergence monitoring at the SB opening location seen in Figure 4.16. Here, the crown monitoring prisms M1 and M2 show downward movement (positive displacement is upward) while the invert monitoring prism M5 moves upward. Note that while there is a difference between the model results and the field convergence measurements of the opening ring, the difference between prism M1 and M5 is predicted well by the model. Following the excavation of TH-5, no work is done in the cross-passage for approximately two weeks (around the time of Christmas), excluding the excavation of B-3 on day 23. During these two weeks, no significant changes in loading are observed (Figure 4.15). Following the excavation of B-4, the thrust force decreases and continues to decrease as B-5 is excavated. However, this decrease in thrust force is not predicted by the 3D model. For bending moments, the 3D model is still in agreement with the field measurements, as squatting behavior seen by another decrease in bending moment as a result of the excavation of B-4 and B-5. The convergence monitoring data also continues to show the squatting trend with a big increase in displacements after the excavation of B4 (Figure 4.16). When the last top-heading, TH-6 is excavated exposing the SB tunnel segments, Figure 15a shows an increase in measured thrust force predicted by the model as well with only a lower magnitude, following a sharp decrease in measured thrust force as a result of the excavation of the last bench, B-6 that is not predicted by the model. The bending moments field measurements are still in agreement with the model prediction showing an increase in bending moment as a result of the last bench excavation.

Figure 4.15. SB tunnel (break-in location) adjacent ring location B: (a) thrust and (b) bending moment from strain gauge monitoring and the 3D model lining deformation vs. time in days after break-out.

Figure 4.16. SB tunnel (break-in location) field convergence monitoring and the 3D model lining deformation (a) opening ring and (b) adjacent ring vs. time in days after break-out. The color legend correlates to the monitoring point color position on the right. Field convergence monitoring is shown by lines and markers without fill, and the 3D model lining deformation results are shown by full markers.

The model predicted shear forces that develop in the bicone dowels around the break-in opening are shown in Figure 4.17. As observed at the break-out side after ring installation, no load is taken by the bicones dowels before any cross-passage activities begin. As the cross-passage excavation advances towards the break-in tunnel, a slow increase in shear force is observed. For the bicone dowels connecting the adjacent ring to the opening ring, a sharp increase in both tangential and radial force is seen after the excavation of the last round of top-heading excavation. Similar to the break-out side, almost no load is taken by the bicone dowels connecting the two opening rings. However, unlike at the break-out side, this is seen before the rings are cut open. At the break-in side, the loading mechanism is different; first the bicone dowel shear load develops as a result of the differential deformation between the adjacent rings and the opening rings. The opening ring squats more as the last rounds of top-heading and bench expose the opening ring removing all confinement, while the adjacent ring is only partially exposed, leaving some ground resistance to squatting deformations. The vertical symmetry around the cross-passage axis results in a no differential displacement between the opening rings and low forces in the bicone dowels connecting the opening rings.

Similarly to the bicone dowels loading process, the vertical steel props thrust force increases gradually as the cross-passage excavation advances towards the break-in tunnel (Figure 4.17c). A sharp increase in thrust force is seen after the excavation of B-5, followed by a 40% decrease of thrust force after the excavation of TH-6 and B-6. In the last stage when the break-in opening is formed, a 40% increase in thrust force is observed. However, this final force is lower than the thrust force seen after the excavation of B-5.

Figure 4.17. Temporary support elements forces predicted by 3D modeling at the SB tunnel (break-in opening) vs. time in days from break-out. Bicone dowels shear forces (a) tangential shear forces and (b) radial shear forces. The color legend correlates to the bicone dowel color position in the top right figure. Filled markers show the bicone dowels connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring, and the unfilled markers show the bicone dowels connecting the two opening rings. (c) Predicted steel prop thrust force.

Figure 4.18 shows the opening ring and the adjacent ring bending moment and thrust force diagrams, where selected stages are presented. While the final bending moment and thrust force diagrams are similar to that of the break-out (NB) tunnel, the thrust force in the opening ring first increases as the excavation advances (as seen after the excavation of TH-4), and only after the excavation of B-5 a gradual decrease occurs. Even before the break-in opening is formed after the excavation of B-5, the steel props take a considerable amount of the load (as can be seen in Figure 4.18c), matching the decrease in thrust force in the opening rings at the area bridged by the steel props (Figure 4.18d). As seen for the adjacent ring in Figure 4.15, both the adjacent ring (Figure 5.18a) and the opening ring (Figure 4.18c) show a gradual squatting behavior as the cross-passage excavation advances.

Figure 4.18. Segmental lining loads at the (a) & (b) adjacent ring and (c) & (d) opening ring of the break-in (SB) tunnel. (a) & (c) show bending moments (kN-m/m) and (b) & (d) show thrust force (kN/m) diagrams. The position of the cross-passage opening is shown by the shaded area.

1.21.4 Support Elements Capacity Considerations

As the segmental lining around the opening serves as the initial and final support system and must remain watertight and within serviceability condition, cross-passage support elements must remain within allowable capacity. Figure 4.19 shows that the shear bicone dowels do stay within their allowable capacity for the case described above. Figure 4.19 also shows the bicone dowels shear forces from an additional 3D model where no vertical steel props were installed, and the opening rings hoop thrust forces transfers to the adjacent rings through the bicones dowels and joints friction. For this case without steel props, the bicone dowel shear force is higher than the allowable bicone dowel capacity by 20%. By improving the reinforcement configuration around the bicone dowels, an increase in the bicone-concrete shear force capacity can be increased by as much as 60%, as shown by Gehwolf et al. (2016) and requires additional testing.

As the segmental lining around the opening must remain in serviceability condition, the thrust-moment combination must remain within the reinforced concrete allowable thrust-moment envelope. Figures 5.12 and 5.18 show that the most critical points are at the opening rings above and below the opening where the thrust force is very low, and the bending moment is very high. At the adjacent ring, high bending moments develop at the spring-line close to the opening; however, combined with high thrust forces, these areas are less critical than the opening rings above and below the opening.

Figure 4.19. Bicone dowels predicted shear force at the (a) break-out (NB) tunnel and (b) break-in (SB) tunnel vs. time in days from break-out. The color legend correlates to the bicone dowel color position in Figures 5.12 and 5.18. Full markers show the bicone dowels connecting the opening ring to the adjacent ring, and the markers without fill show the bicone dowels connecting the two opening rings

1.22 Conclusions

Cross-passage construction is a complex 3D ground-structure interaction problem. Despite the complexity of cross-passage construction, little research is available in the literature on cross-passage openings in segmentally lined tunnels. In this paper, an advanced 3D ground-structure interaction numerical model together with field measurements is used to achieve a better understanding of the load development in support systems of cross passages, mainly at the openings created in the segmental lining of the running tunnels. The 3D numerical models allowed the prediction and analysis the response of the different cross-passage components not instrumented in the field, such as the shear bicone dowels shear forces, vertical steel prop forces, and segmental lining load diagrams. The presented model details all the complex ground-structure interaction aspects taken into account for both shield tunneling (running tunnels) and cross-passage excavation. The advanced 3D numerical model presented here captures the important components in both shield tunneling and cross-passage excavation, including the jointed segmental lining coupling effects, running tunnels relaxation due to pre-convergence, the non-liner soil behavior, removal of segmental lining at the cross-passage opening, temporary support elements (shear dowels and vertical steel props), step by step top-heading and bench excavation, initial shotcrete layer, full shotcrete thickness at a lag of one stage, and shotcrete time-dependent hardening.

The results show the difference between the loading process of the break-in and break-out. The loading process at the break-out side is controlled mostly by the saw-cutting of the opening and the elements distributing the hoop load around the opening. At the break-in side, considerable lining loads develop prior to the saw cutting as a result of the advance of the cross-passage tunnel and the relaxation of the ground confining the break-in area. This relaxation results in differential deformation between the adjacent rings and the opening rings, inducing considerable loads. The opening ring at the break-in tunnel squats more as the last rounds of top-heading and bench expose the opening ring removing all confinement, while the adjacent ring is only partially exposed, leaving some ground resistance to squatting deformations.

The most critical points in regards to the load capacity of the cross-passage opening support elements are segmental lining above and below the openings, and the bicone dowels shear capacity. Above and below the opening, the most unfavorable thrust-moment combination is found with zero thrust force and very high bending moments. When combined with vertical steel props, the bicone dowels shear force is found to remain within their allowable capacity for the Northgate Link case. From an additional analysis without the vertical steel props, it was found that the bicone dowels shear force exceeded the allowable capacity by only 20%. The gap between the allowable capacity and the predicted load can be bridged by improving the reinforcement configuration around the bicone dowels; however, additional testing is needed.

5.1.

GENERAL DISCUSSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

This project has allowed several contributions to the knowledge and the understanding of ground-structure interaction of segmentally lined tunnels constructed using pressure balance TBM tunneling and of cross-passage openings in segmentally lined tunnels. While conclusions are detailed in each chapter, the following sections discuss the most important conclusions followed by recommendations for further research.

1.23 Ground-Structure Interaction for Pressure Balance TBM tunneling in Soft Ground

The influence of face and shield annulus pressure on tunnel lining loads is investigated using 3D numerical modeling and rare segmental lining load field measurement data (Chapter 3). For pressure balance TBMs where the shield annulus is full of pressurized material, the final lining loads are controlled by the chamber and shield annulus pressure. Drops of the chamber pressure are common in EPBM tunneling during excavation standstill. These chamber pressure drops were found to result in significant influence on tunnel lining thrust forces. As a result of the pressure drop at the chamber and the shield annulus, the stress redistributes, decreasing around the shield and increasing around the last installed rings (closest to the shield tail). This results in an increase in the lining thrust force of the last installed rings, with the highest increase in the last ring installed, reducing farther away behind the tail. The rings installed supporting the ground that experienced the pressure drop will develop lower lining loads due to the higher degree of relaxation as a result of the pressure drop. The proposed 3D numerical model simplifying the TBM shield with the shield annulus pressure can be used to predict the segmental lining structural forces without the need for complex modeling of the shield and soil-shield interaction. However, this assumption must be validated by demonstrating that the maximum tunnel displacement is smaller than the annulus gap.

The accuracy of the LDP solution is critical for a reliable prediction of the lining forces in 2D modeling and in analytical solutions. Based on the importance of the TBM support pressure for the prediction of lining loads, the ability to predict the amount of convergence prior to lining installation relies on incorporating the support pressure applied during excavation. Furthermore, the HSS model is able to generate more realistic soil response in terms of non-linearity, stress dependency, and inelasticity compared to the EPP the MC model. Chapter 4 discusses the investigation of the longitudinal displacement behavior and proposes an LDP solution for soft ground tunneling characterized by the HSS model and constructed using pressure balance TBMs. The results show the difference between the ground response of a tunnel excavated in EPP soil compared to a tunnel excavated in HSS soil. The main differences arise from the fact that in the HSS model, there is no fully elastic zone around the tunnel, and plastic strains (as part of the elastoplastic behavior described by Eq. 4.7) develop from the initiation of shearing. It was also found that the calculation of LDPs assuming linear-elastic or the EPP soil behavior compared to the more realistic HSS model can result in overestimation of the pre-convergence that will occur prior to

liner installation. This overestimation of the pre-convergence by EPP MC was shown to be as much as 20%. Together with GRCs that show no significant difference between the HSS and MC (when put in terms of normalized values), the use of EPP soil models can result in underestimation of support loads for ground better characterized by the HSS model. A comprehensive parametric analysis was conducted for the development and validation of the HSS LDP equation (Eq. 4.16). The parametric analysis included a variation of internal support pressures (allowing different degrees of elastoplastic behavior), and a variation of selected input parameters of the HSS model. The results showed a very good ability of the HSS LDP solution to predict the tunnel LDP in HSS material.

1.24 Ground-Structure Interaction of Cross-Passage Tunnels Connecting Segmentally Lined Tunnels

An advanced 3D ground-structure interaction numerical model was proposed and validated with rare field data from the Seattle Sound Transit Northgate Link tunnel project, including data from strain gauges installed in segmental lining rings and convergence monitoring (Chapter 5). This 3D ground-structure interaction model presented in detail for the first time in available literature was used to achieve a better understanding of the load development in support systems of cross passages, mainly at the openings created in the segmental lining of the running tunnels. The results show the difference between the loading process of the break-in and break-out. The loading process at the break-out side is controlled mostly by the saw-cutting of the opening and the support elements distributing the hoop load around the opening. At the break-in side, considerable lining loads develop prior to the saw cutting as a result of the advance of the cross-passage tunnel towards the break-in and the relaxation of the ground confining the break-in area. This relaxation results in differential deformation between the adjacent rings and the opening rings, inducing considerable loads. The most critical points in regards to the load capacity of the cross-passage opening support elements are segmental lining above and below the openings, and the bicone dowels shear capacity. Above and below the opening, the most unfavorable thrust-moment combination is found with close to zero thrust force and very high bending moments. When combined with vertical steel props, the bicone dowels shear force is found to remain within their allowable capacity for the Northgate Link case. From an additional analysis without the vertical steel props, it was found that the bicone dowels shear force exceeded the allowable capacity by only 20%.

1.25 Recommendations for Further Research

The research conducted as part of this project contributed to the knowledge and the understanding of ground-structure interaction. At the same time, it also highlighted some aspects that require further research. The following aspects are recommended for future research:

- Investigation of the validity of the proposed 3D model for pressure balanced mechanized tunneling for smaller shield annulus gaps and different pressure profiles between the face and the shield tail.

- Measurement of field LDPs using shape accelerometer array (also referred to as horizontal inclinometer) for further investigation of soft ground LDP.
- Further investigation on ground-structure interaction of cross-passages should be done for different ground properties, main tunnels vs. cross-passage diameter ratios, cross-passage excavation sequences, temporary support elements (full ring beam, steel segments, types of shear dowels), and conditions of circumferential joint coupling.
- Investigation of circumferential joint frictional coupling mechanism by field measurement of normal force at the circumferential joints.
- Investigate the reliability of the circumferential joint coupling for cross-passage design.

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Technology Transfer Activities

by

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Strain gage data from cross-passage 35

Intrados

Sample	Timestamp	Ext1Sample	Strain
1	8/17/2015 18:15	375	-107.340006
2	8/17/2015 22:15	376	-106.599206
3	8/18/2015 2:15	376	-106.599206
4	8/18/2015 6:15	375	-107.340006
5	8/18/2015 10:15	376	-106.599206
6	8/18/2015 14:15	375	-107.340006
7	8/18/2015 18:15	376	-106.599206
8	8/18/2015 22:15	376	-106.599206
9	8/19/2015 2:15	376	-106.599206
10	8/19/2015 6:15	375	-107.340006
11	8/19/2015 10:15	375	-107.340006
12	8/19/2015 14:15	376	-106.599206
13	8/19/2015 18:15	375	-107.340006
14	8/19/2015 22:15	375	-107.340006
15	8/20/2015 2:15	376	-106.599206
16	8/20/2015 6:15	375	-107.340006
17	8/20/2015 10:15	376	-106.599206
18	8/20/2015 14:15	376	-106.599206
19	8/20/2015 18:15	374	-108.080806
20	8/20/2015 22:15	374	-108.080806
21	8/21/2015 2:15	374	-108.080806
22	8/21/2015 6:15	376	-106.599206
23	8/21/2015 10:15	376	-106.599206
24	8/21/2015 14:15	374	-108.080806
25	8/21/2015 18:15	374	-108.080806
26	8/21/2015 22:15	373	-108.821606
27	8/22/2015 2:15	373	-108.821606
28	8/22/2015 6:15	373	-108.821606

Extrados

Sample	Timestamp	Ext1Sample	Strain
1	8/17/2015 18:18	325	-157.6099815
2	8/17/2015 22:18	324	-158.4099815
3	8/18/2015 2:18	325	-157.6099815
4	8/18/2015 6:18	325	-157.6099815
5	8/18/2015 10:18	324	-158.4099815
6	8/18/2015 14:18	324	-158.4099815
7	8/18/2015 18:18	324	-158.4099815
8	8/18/2015 22:18	324	-158.4099815
9	8/19/2015 2:18	325	-157.6099815
10	8/19/2015 6:18	325	-157.6099815
11	8/19/2015 10:18	324	-158.4099815
12	8/19/2015 14:18	323	-159.2099815
13	8/19/2015 18:18	324	-158.4099815
14	8/19/2015 22:18	324	-158.4099815
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417	10/26/2015 2:15	385	-99.93200576	417	10/25/2015 18:23	335	-149.6099814
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419	10/26/2015 10:15	385	-99.93200576	419	10/26/2015 2:23	334	-150.4099814
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474	10/31/2015 23:08	387	-98.45040572	474	10/31/2015 11:09	334	-150.4099814
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596	11/11/2015 2:03	390	-96.22800565	596	11/10/2015 15:09	341	-144.8099813
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1811	3/4/2016 10:05	394	-93.26480556	1811	5/23/2016 21:20	344	-142.4099813
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2244	4/9/2016 13:14	392	-94.7464056	2244	6/26/2016 22:48	339	-146.4099813
2245	4/9/2016 15:14	391	-95.48720562	2245	6/27/2016 0:48	340	-145.6099813
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2268	4/11/2016 13:14	390	-96.22800565	2268	6/28/2016 22:48	339	-146.4099813

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2293	5/13/2016 1:48	360	-118.4520063	2293	7/1/2016 0:48	339	-146.4099813
2294	5/13/2016 3:48	361	-117.7112063	2294	7/1/2016 2:48	338	-147.2099813
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2307	5/14/2016 5:48	360	-118.4520063	2307	7/2/2016 4:48	336	-148.8099813
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2323	5/15/2016 13:48	365	-114.7480062	2323	7/3/2016 12:48	337	-148.0099813
2324	5/15/2016 15:48	365	-114.7480062	2324	7/3/2016 14:48	337	-148.0099813
2325	5/15/2016 17:48	366	-114.0072062	2325	7/3/2016 16:48	337	-148.0099813
2326	5/15/2016 19:48	365	-114.7480062	2326	7/3/2016 18:48	336	-148.8099813
2327	5/15/2016 21:48	366	-114.0072062	2327	7/3/2016 20:48	337	-148.0099813
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2501	5/30/2016 9:48	359	-119.1928064	2501	8/22/2016 14:28	378	-115.2099808
2502	5/30/2016 11:48	359	-119.1928064	2502	8/22/2016 16:28	379	-114.4099808
2503	5/30/2016 13:48	359	-119.1928064	2503	8/22/2016 18:28	379	-114.4099808
2504	5/30/2016 15:48	359	-119.1928064	2504	8/22/2016 20:28	379	-114.4099808
2505	5/30/2016 17:48	358	-119.9336064	2505	8/22/2016 22:28	377	-116.0099809
2506	5/30/2016 19:48	358	-119.9336064	2506	8/23/2016 0:28	377	-116.0099809
2507	5/30/2016 21:48	358	-119.9336064	2507	8/23/2016 2:28	377	-116.0099809
2508	5/30/2016 23:48	356	-121.4152064	2508	8/23/2016 4:28	377	-116.0099809
2509	5/31/2016 1:48	357	-120.6744064	2509	8/23/2016 6:28	377	-116.0099809
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2512	5/31/2016 7:48	358	-119.9336064	2512	8/23/2016 12:28	377	-116.0099809
2513	5/31/2016 9:48	360	-118.4520063	2513	8/23/2016 14:28	377	-116.0099809
2514	5/31/2016 11:48	360	-118.4520063	2514	8/23/2016 16:28	378	-115.2099808
2515	5/31/2016 13:48	359	-119.1928064	2515	8/23/2016 18:28	378	-115.2099808
2516	5/31/2016 15:48	358	-119.9336064	2516	8/23/2016 20:28	378	-115.2099808
2517	5/31/2016 17:48	357	-120.6744064	2517	8/23/2016 22:28	377	-116.0099809
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2519	5/31/2016 21:48	356	-121.4152064	2519	8/24/2016 2:28	377	-116.0099809
2520	5/31/2016 23:48	355	-122.1560065	2520	8/24/2016 4:28	377	-116.0099809
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2526	6/1/2016 11:48	357	-120.6744064	2526	8/24/2016 16:28	384	-110.4099808
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2529	6/1/2016 17:48	356	-121.4152064	2529	8/24/2016 22:28	384	-110.4099808
2530	6/1/2016 19:48	355	-122.1560065	2530	8/25/2016 0:28	385	-109.6099808
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2545	6/3/2016 1:48	355	-122.1560065	2545	8/26/2016 6:28	383	-111.2099808
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2547	6/3/2016 5:48	355	-122.1560065	2547	8/26/2016 10:28	384	-110.4099808
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2571	6/5/2016 5:48	353	-123.6376065	2571	8/28/2016 10:28	376	-116.8099809
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2580	6/5/2016 23:48	351	-125.1192065	2580	8/29/2016 4:28	374	-118.4099809
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2596	6/7/2016 7:48	352	-124.3784065	2596	8/30/2016 12:28	375	-117.6099809
2597	6/7/2016 9:48	352	-124.3784065	2597	8/30/2016 14:28	375	-117.6099809
2598	6/7/2016 11:48	351	-125.1192065	2598	8/30/2016 16:28	375	-117.6099809
2599	6/7/2016 13:48	352	-124.3784065	2599	8/30/2016 18:28	376	-116.8099809
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2612	6/8/2016 15:48	351	-125.1192065	2612	8/31/2016 20:28	371	-120.8099809
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2633	6/10/2016 9:48	352	-124.3784065	2633	9/2/2016 14:28	369	-122.409981
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2635	6/10/2016 13:48	354	-122.8968065	2635	9/2/2016 18:28	369	-122.409981
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2643	6/11/2016 5:48	352	-124.3784065	2643	9/3/2016 10:28	368	-123.209981
2644	6/11/2016 7:48	353	-123.6376065	2644	9/3/2016 12:28	369	-122.409981
2645	6/11/2016 9:48	353	-123.6376065	2645	9/3/2016 14:28	369	-122.409981
2646	6/11/2016 11:48	353	-123.6376065	2646	9/3/2016 16:28	368	-123.209981
2647	6/11/2016 13:48	353	-123.6376065	2647	9/3/2016 18:28	369	-122.409981
2648	6/11/2016 15:48	353	-123.6376065	2648	9/3/2016 20:28	371	-120.8099809
2649	6/11/2016 17:48	353	-123.6376065	2649	9/3/2016 22:28	369	-122.409981
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2653	6/12/2016 1:48	351	-125.1192065	2653	9/4/2016 6:28	368	-123.209981
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2661	6/12/2016 17:48	352	-124.3784065	2661	9/4/2016 22:28	369	-122.409981
2662	6/12/2016 19:48	352	-124.3784065	2662	9/5/2016 0:28	369	-122.409981
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2685	6/14/2016 17:48	352	-124.3784065	2685	9/6/2016 22:28	368	-123.209981
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2876	6/30/2016 8:48	350	-125.8600066	2876	10/1/2016 13:05	338	-147.2099813

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2879	6/30/2016 14:48	346	-128.8232067	2879	10/1/2016 19:05	338	-147.2099813
2880	6/30/2016 16:48	346	-128.8232067	2880	10/1/2016 21:05	338	-147.2099813
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2890	7/1/2016 12:48	348	-127.3416066	2890	10/2/2016 17:05	338	-147.2099813
2891	7/1/2016 14:48	348	-127.3416066	2891	10/2/2016 19:05	338	-147.2099813
2892	7/1/2016 16:48	347	-128.0824066	2892	10/2/2016 21:05	338	-147.2099813
2893	7/1/2016 18:48	345	-129.5640067	2893	10/2/2016 23:05	338	-147.2099813
2894	7/1/2016 20:48	345	-129.5640067	2894	10/3/2016 1:05	338	-147.2099813
2895	7/1/2016 22:48	346	-128.8232067	2895	10/3/2016 3:05	337	-148.0099813
2896	7/2/2016 0:48	345	-129.5640067	2896	10/3/2016 5:05	338	-147.2099813
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2903	7/2/2016 14:48	347	-128.0824066	2903	10/3/2016 19:05	337	-148.0099813
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2905	7/2/2016 18:48	345	-129.5640067	2905	10/3/2016 23:05	337	-148.0099813
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2914	7/3/2016 12:48	349	-126.6008066	2914	10/4/2016 17:05	336	-148.8099813
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2927	7/4/2016 14:48	347	-128.0824066	2927	10/5/2016 19:05	346	-140.8099812
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2929	7/4/2016 18:48	347	-128.0824066	2929	10/5/2016 23:05	345	-141.6099812
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2931	7/4/2016 22:48	347	-128.0824066	2931	10/6/2016 3:05	346	-140.8099812
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2937	7/5/2016 10:48	348	-127.3416066	2937	10/6/2016 15:05	346	-140.8099812
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2939	7/5/2016 14:48	349	-126.6008066	2939	10/6/2016 19:05	346	-140.8099812
2940	7/5/2016 16:48	348	-127.3416066	2940	10/6/2016 21:05	346	-140.8099812

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2943	7/5/2016 22:48	346	-128.8232067	2943	10/7/2016 3:05	345	-141.6099812
2944	7/6/2016 0:48	342	-131.7864068	2944	10/7/2016 5:05	345	-141.6099812
2945	7/6/2016 2:48	346	-128.8232067	2945	10/7/2016 7:05	346	-140.8099812
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2952	8/10/2016 0:28	316	-151.0472074	2952	10/7/2016 21:05	346	-140.8099812
2953	8/10/2016 2:28	315	-151.7880074	2953	10/7/2016 23:05	346	-140.8099812
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2960	8/10/2016 16:28	318	-149.5656073	2960	10/8/2016 13:05	345	-141.6099812
2961	8/10/2016 18:28	316	-151.0472074	2961	10/8/2016 15:05	345	-141.6099812
2962	8/10/2016 20:28	316	-151.0472074	2962	10/8/2016 17:05	343	-143.2099813
2963	8/10/2016 22:28	315	-151.7880074	2963	10/8/2016 19:05	345	-141.6099812
2964	8/11/2016 0:28	314	-152.5288074	2964	10/8/2016 21:05	345	-141.6099812
2965	8/11/2016 2:28	313	-153.2696074	2965	10/8/2016 23:05	345	-141.6099812
2966	8/11/2016 4:28	314	-152.5288074	2966	10/9/2016 1:05	345	-141.6099812
2967	8/11/2016 6:28	313	-153.2696074	2967	10/9/2016 3:05	344	-142.4099813
2968	8/11/2016 8:28	315	-151.7880074	2968	10/9/2016 5:05	344	-142.4099813
2969	8/11/2016 10:28	316	-151.0472074	2969	10/9/2016 7:05	343	-143.2099813
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2971	8/11/2016 14:28	315	-151.7880074	2971	10/9/2016 11:05	344	-142.4099813
2972	8/11/2016 16:28	315	-151.7880074	2972	10/9/2016 13:05	343	-143.2099813

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2975	8/11/2016 22:28	311	-154.7512075	2975	10/9/2016 19:05	343	-143.2099813
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3005	8/14/2016 10:28	311	-154.7512075	3005	10/12/2016 7:05	345	-141.6099812
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3008	8/14/2016 16:28	311	-154.7512075	3008	10/12/2016 13:05	343	-143.2099813
3009	8/14/2016 18:28	310	-155.4920075	3009	10/12/2016 15:05	343	-143.2099813
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3011	8/14/2016 22:28	306	-158.4552076	3011	10/12/2016 19:05	344	-142.4099813
3012	8/15/2016 0:28	306	-158.4552076	3012	10/12/2016 21:05	344	-142.4099813
3013	8/15/2016 2:28	307	-157.7144076	3013	10/12/2016 23:05	346	-140.8099812
3014	8/15/2016 4:28	307	-157.7144076	3014	10/13/2016 1:05	345	-141.6099812
3015	8/15/2016 6:28	308	-156.9736075	3015	10/13/2016 3:05	343	-143.2099813
3016	8/15/2016 8:28	308	-156.9736075	3016	10/13/2016 5:05	343	-143.2099813
3017	8/15/2016 10:28	309	-156.2328075	3017	10/13/2016 7:05	342	-144.0099813
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3036	8/17/2016 0:28	307	-157.7144076	3036	10/14/2016 21:05	338	-147.2099813

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3045	8/17/2016 18:28	308	-156.9736075	3045	10/15/2016 15:05	338	-147.2099813
3046	8/17/2016 20:28	307	-157.7144076	3046	10/15/2016 17:05	338	-147.2099813
3047	8/17/2016 22:28	306	-158.4552076	3047	10/15/2016 19:05	338	-147.2099813
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3069	8/19/2016 18:28	302	-161.4184077	3069	10/17/2016 15:05	337	-148.0099813
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3083	8/20/2016 22:28	300	-162.9000077	3083	10/18/2016 19:05	335	-149.6099814
3084	8/21/2016 0:28	301	-162.1592077	3084	10/18/2016 21:05	336	-148.8099813
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3096	8/22/2016 0:28	302	-161.4184077	3096	10/19/2016 21:05	334	-150.4099814
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3104	8/22/2016 16:28	306	-158.4552076	3104	10/20/2016 13:05	335	-149.6099814
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3110	8/23/2016 4:28	303	-160.6776077	3110	10/21/2016 1:05	335	-149.6099814
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3119	8/23/2016 22:28	298	-164.3816078	3119	10/21/2016 19:05	332	-152.0099814
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3123	8/24/2016 6:28	300	-162.9000077	3123	10/22/2016 3:05	332	-152.0099814
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3131	8/24/2016 22:28	297	-165.1224078	3131	10/22/2016 19:05	331	-152.8099814
3132	8/25/2016 0:28	297	-165.1224078	3132	10/22/2016 21:05	332	-152.0099814

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3134	8/25/2016 4:28	296	-165.8632078	3134	10/23/2016 1:05	330	-153.6099814
3135	8/25/2016 6:28	298	-164.3816078	3135	10/23/2016 3:05	329	-154.4099814
3136	8/25/2016 8:28	299	-163.6408077	3136	10/23/2016 5:05	328	-155.2099814
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3141	8/25/2016 18:28	299	-163.6408077	3141	10/23/2016 15:05	329	-154.4099814
3142	8/25/2016 20:28	297	-165.1224078	3142	10/23/2016 17:05	329	-154.4099814
3143	8/25/2016 22:28	294	-167.3448079	3143	10/23/2016 19:05	328	-155.2099814
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3145	8/26/2016 2:28	293	-168.0856079	3145	10/23/2016 23:05	328	-155.2099814
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3211	8/31/2016 14:28	299	-163.6408077	3211	10/29/2016 11:05	323	-159.2099815
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3220	9/1/2016 8:28	299	-163.6408077	3220	10/30/2016 5:05	320	-161.6099815
3221	9/1/2016 10:28	298	-164.3816078	3221	10/30/2016 7:05	320	-161.6099815
3222	9/1/2016 12:28	299	-163.6408077	3222	10/30/2016 9:05	321	-160.8099815
3223	9/1/2016 14:28	300	-162.9000077	3223	10/30/2016 11:05	322	-160.0099815
3224	9/1/2016 16:28	299	-163.6408077	3224	10/30/2016 13:05	321	-160.8099815
3225	9/1/2016 18:28	300	-162.9000077	3225	10/30/2016 15:05	322	-160.0099815
3226	9/1/2016 20:28	299	-163.6408077	3226	10/30/2016 17:05	321	-160.8099815
3227	9/1/2016 22:28	298	-164.3816078	3227	10/30/2016 19:05	321	-160.8099815
3228	9/2/2016 0:28	299	-163.6408077	3228	10/30/2016 21:05	321	-160.8099815

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3234	9/2/2016 12:28	300	-162.9000077	3234	10/31/2016 9:05	322	-160.0099815
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3236	9/2/2016 16:28	301	-162.1592077	3236	10/31/2016 13:05	322	-160.0099815
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3238	9/2/2016 20:28	300	-162.9000077	3238	10/31/2016 17:05	321	-160.8099815
3239	9/2/2016 22:28	299	-163.6408077	3239	10/31/2016 19:05	322	-160.0099815
3240	9/3/2016 0:28	299	-163.6408077	3240	10/31/2016 21:05	321	-160.8099815
3241	9/3/2016 2:28	298	-164.3816078	3241	10/31/2016 23:05	321	-160.8099815
3242	9/3/2016 4:28	299	-163.6408077	3242	11/1/2016 1:05	321	-160.8099815
3243	9/3/2016 6:28	299	-163.6408077	3243	11/1/2016 3:05	321	-160.8099815
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3249	9/3/2016 18:28	301	-162.1592077	3249	11/1/2016 15:05	320	-161.6099815
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3880	11/4/2016 9:06	285	-174.0120081
3881	11/4/2016 11:06	285	-174.0120081
3882	11/4/2016 13:06	286	-173.271208
3883	11/4/2016 15:06	287	-172.530408
3884	11/4/2016 17:06	287	-172.530408
3885	11/4/2016 19:06	287	-172.530408
3886	11/4/2016 21:06	284	-174.7528081
3887	11/4/2016 23:06	282	-176.2344081
3888	11/5/2016 1:06	282	-176.2344081
3889	11/5/2016 3:06	281	-176.9752082
3890	11/5/2016 5:06	281	-176.9752082
3891	11/5/2016 7:06	281	-176.9752082
3892	11/5/2016 9:06	281	-176.9752082
3893	11/5/2016 11:06	282	-176.2344081
3894	11/5/2016 13:06	283	-175.4936081
3895	11/5/2016 15:06	283	-175.4936081
3896	11/5/2016 17:06	283	-175.4936081
3897	11/5/2016 19:06	284	-174.7528081
3898	11/5/2016 21:06	283	-175.4936081
3899	11/5/2016 23:06	284	-174.7528081
3900	11/6/2016 1:06	284	-174.7528081

3901	11/6/2016 3:06	285	-174.0120081
3902	11/6/2016 5:06	285	-174.0120081
3903	11/6/2016 7:06	284	-174.7528081
3904	11/6/2016 9:06	284	-174.7528081
3905	11/6/2016 11:06	286	-173.271208
3906	11/6/2016 13:06	285	-174.0120081
3907	11/6/2016 15:06	286	-173.271208
3908	11/6/2016 17:06	286	-173.271208
3909	11/6/2016 19:06	286	-173.271208
3910	11/6/2016 21:06	284	-174.7528081
3911	11/6/2016 23:06	283	-175.4936081
3912	11/7/2016 1:06	283	-175.4936081
3913	11/7/2016 3:06	283	-175.4936081
3914	11/7/2016 5:06	282	-176.2344081
3915	11/7/2016 7:06	282	-176.2344081
3916	11/7/2016 9:06	283	-175.4936081
3917	11/7/2016 11:06	283	-175.4936081
3918	11/7/2016 13:06	283	-175.4936081
3919	11/7/2016 15:06	283	-175.4936081
3920	11/7/2016 17:06	283	-175.4936081
3921	11/7/2016 19:06	283	-175.4936081
3922	11/7/2016 21:06	282	-176.2344081
3923	11/7/2016 23:06	281	-176.9752082
3924	11/8/2016 1:06	280	-177.7160082
3925	11/8/2016 3:06	280	-177.7160082
3926	11/8/2016 5:06	279	-178.4568082
3927	11/8/2016 7:06	279	-178.4568082
3928	11/8/2016 9:06	280	-177.7160082
3929	11/8/2016 11:06	281	-176.9752082
3930	11/8/2016 13:06	282	-176.2344081
3931	11/8/2016 15:06	283	-175.4936081
3932	11/8/2016 17:06	283	-175.4936081

3933	11/8/2016 19:06	282	-176.2344081
3934	11/8/2016 21:06	281	-176.9752082
3935	11/8/2016 23:06	278	-179.1976082
3936	11/9/2016 1:06	278	-179.1976082
3937	11/9/2016 3:06	279	-178.4568082
3938	11/9/2016 5:06	279	-178.4568082
3939	11/9/2016 7:06	278	-179.1976082
3940	11/9/2016 9:06	279	-178.4568082
3941	11/9/2016 11:06	280	-177.7160082
3942	11/9/2016 13:06	280	-177.7160082
3943	11/9/2016 15:06	281	-176.9752082
3944	11/9/2016 17:06	282	-176.2344081
3945	11/9/2016 19:06	282	-176.2344081
3946	11/9/2016 21:06	282	-176.2344081
3947	11/9/2016 23:06	280	-177.7160082
3948	11/10/2016 1:06	281	-176.9752082
3949	11/10/2016 3:06	281	-176.9752082
3950	11/10/2016 5:06	280	-177.7160082
3951	11/10/2016 7:06	282	-176.2344081
3952	11/10/2016 9:06	282	-176.2344081
3953	11/10/2016 11:06	283	-175.4936081
3954	11/10/2016 13:06	283	-175.4936081
3955	11/10/2016 15:06	285	-174.0120081

APPENDIX B - TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER ACTIVITIES

B.1 ACCOMPLISHMENTS

B.1.1 WHAT WAS DONE? WHAT WAS LEARNED?

- Segmental tunnel lining strain measurements were collected from the Soundtransit Northgate Link project in Seattle.
- Segmental tunnel lining load development during pressure balance tunneling was studied using 3D numerical modeling and field data of measured thrust forces and bending moments from the Northgate Link project in Seattle.
- Cross passage openings in segmental tunnel lining load development was studied using 3D numerical modeling and field data from the Northgate Link project in Seattle.
- A new longitudinal displacement profile equation was developed for a more accurate prediction of tunnel pre-convergence in soft ground pressure balance tunneling.
- An advanced 3D ground-structure interaction numerical model was presented and validated with field data for the first time in available literature.
- The research findings can be used to assist the Department of Transportation and its subcontractors to achieve a more efficient design of segmental lining and cross-passage openings.

1.2. How have the results been disseminated?

- The results were presented at World Tunnel Congress 2018 in Dubai
- The results were presented at the North American Tunneling Conference 2018 in Washington, D.C
- The results were presented at Rapid Excavation and Tunneling Conference 2019, Chicago, IL.
- The results were presented at the 1st and 2nd UTC-UTI workshops

B.2 PARTICIPANTS AND COLLABORATING ORGANIZATIONS

Sound Transit, Seattle, WA

Jay Dee Contractors, Seattle, WA

L-7 Services, Golden, CO

B.3 OUTPUTS

Journal publications

Epel, T., Mooney, M., Gutierrez, M., 2020. The Influence of Face and Shield Annulus Pressure on Tunnel Liner Load Development. Tunneling and Underground Space Technology. Manuscript submitted for publication.

Presentations

Epel, T., Mooney, M., Gutierrez, M., Braun, K., DiPonio, M., Long, N. 2018a. Analysis methodologies comparison of estimated and measured precast segment liner loads developed during construction of twin EPB TBM tunnels in Seattle. In Proc. of World Tunnel Congress 2018.

Epel, T., Mooney, M., Gutierrez, M., Braun, K., DiPonio, M., Long, N. 2018b. Ground-liner interaction during Seattle Northgate Link cross-passage construction. In Proc. of North American Tunneling Conference 2018, Washington, D.C., pp. 341–349.

Epel, T., Mooney, M., & Gutierrez, M. 2019. Liner Load Estimation for Soft Ground Pressure Balance TBM Shield Tunnel Projects. In Proc. of Rapid Excavation and Tunneling Conference 2019, Chicago, IL, pp. 109–119.

Workshops

Tamir Epel, “Understanding Cross Passage Ground-Structure Interaction Using Data from the Seattle Northgate Link Transit Extension Project”. First Workshop of the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure, Golden, CO, February 19, 2018

Tamir Epel, “Examination of Segmental Liner Loading for Soft Ground Tunnels: Design Approaches vs. Actual Behavior”. Second Workshop of the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure, Golden, CO, October 17, 2019

B.4 OUTCOMES

- The developed 3D numerical model for pressure balance TBM tunneling can be used to predict tunnel lining loads more accurately for different support pressures used during construction.
- The developed 3D numerical model for cross-passages with openings in segmental tunnel lining can be used to predict loads in temporary support elements more accurately and reduce uncertainty.
- The new longitudinal displacement profile equation allows for a better ability to predict liner loads in soft ground pressure balance TBM tunneling without the need for 3D numerical analysis.

B.5 IMPACTS

- Using the improved tool developed in this research project, tunnel lining design can be more efficient resulting in more cost-effective and safer tunnel structures.